

**STRUCTURAL AND INITIAL PERMEABILITY STUDIES
OF NANOCRYSTALLINE $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$
PREPARED BY COMBUSTION TECHNIQUE**

*A Dissertation Submitted to the Department of Physics,
Bangladesh University of Engineering & Technology, Dhaka, in
Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Degree of
Master of Philosophy (M. Phil.) in Physics*

SUBMITTED

By

Muhammod Abu Mohshin Quraishi

**EXAMINATION ROLL NO. : 100614042F
SESSION : October 2006**

**DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS
BANGLADESH UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY
DHAKA 1000, BANGLADESH
September 2011**

CANDIDATE'S DECLARATION

It is hereby declared that this thesis or any part of it has not been submitted elsewhere for the award of any degree or diploma.

Muhammod Abu Mohshin Quraishi

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

CERTIFICATION OF THESIS

The Thesis titled “**STRUCTURAL AND INITIAL PERMEABILITY STUDIES OF NANOCRYSTALLINE $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ PREPARED BY COMBUSTION TECHNIQUE**” submitted by Muhammad Abu Mohshin Quraishi, Roll No.: 100614042F, Session: October 2006, has been accepted as satisfactory in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of **Master of Philosophy (M. Phil)** in Physics on September 24, 2011.

BOARD OF EXAMINERS

1. (_____) Chairman
Dr. A. K. M. Akther Hossain (Supervisor)
Professor, Department of Physics,
BUET, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh
2. (_____) Member
Head, Department of Physics, Ex-Officio
BUET, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh
3. (_____) Member
Dr. Md.Abu Hashan Bhuiyan
Professor, Department of Physics,
BUET, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh.
4. (_____) Member
Dr. Nasreen Akter,
Assistant Professor, Department of Physics,
BUET, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh.
5. (_____) Member
Dr. Kazi Monowar Abedin (External)
Professor, Department of Physics,
University of Dhaka, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh.

BANGLADESH UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

First of all, I am expressing all my praises and devotion to the Almighty Allah (SWT)-Who is Merciful to all and Who enabled me to perform this thesis work, and to submit this by His wish.

I have deepest sense of gratitude to my supervisor Dr. A.K.M. Akther Hossain, Professor and Head, Department of Physics, BUET, for his scholastic supervision time to time, constructive criticism and his non-payable sacrifices. Words always remain insufficient to express his working capacities and endless enthusiasm in scientific rigorousness for innovative investigations. This always becomes the everlasting source of inspiration for his students.

I would like to express special thanks to Professor Dr. Md. Abu Hashan Bhuiyan, Professor Dr. Jiban Podder, Professor Dr. Md. Feroz Alam Khan, Professor Dr. Md. Mostak Hossain, Mrs. Fahima Khanam, Dr. Afia Begum, Dr. Md. Forhad Mina, Dr. Md. Rafi Uddin, Dr. Nasreen Akter, and all other teachers of the Physics Department of BUET, for their constructive suggestion and cooperation.

I am grateful to the authority of BCSIR, for giving me permission to use their apparatus. I wish to thank my senior research worker Farhad Alam, Hamidur Rahman Khan (Department of Physics, BUET) specially for their cooperation throughout the study. I am especially grateful to my friends and classmates Md. Belal Hossain and Md. Omar Faruq, for their inspiration, encouragement and constant support throughout the thesis work.

I am highly indebted and grateful to BUET authority for providing me financial support for this research work. Thanks to all staff of the Physics department, for their constant cooperation.

(Md. Abu Mohshin Quraishi)

Author

Dedicated to.....

MY WIFE

ABSTRACT

The nanocrystalline $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ferrites with $x = 0.00, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40$ and 0.44 have been synthesized by combustion technique. The particle size of various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ is found to be 9 to 30 nm range. Disc- and toroid-shaped samples are prepared and sintered at various temperatures (1200, 1250, 1300 and 1350°C) in air for 1 hour. Structural and surface morphology are studied by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and high resolution optical microscope, respectively. The magnetic properties of these compositions are characterized by high frequency (10 kHz-120MHz) complex permeability measurements. The influence of microstructure and sintering temperatures on the complex permeability of these ferrites are discussed. A possible correlation among sintering temperature, average grain size and density is also discussed.

The XRD patterns of all samples clearly indicate the formation of single phase spinel structure. It is found that the lattice constant increases linearly with increasing Li contents obeying Vegard's law. This is due to the fact that the ionic radius of Li^+ (0.76Å) and Fe^{3+} (0.645 Å) are greater than that of Mn^{2+} (0.67Å). The grain size increases with increasing Li content in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$. The bulk density shows a decreasing trend with Li substitution. As the sintering temperature increases, bulk density increases, therefore porosity decreases for all samples. The real part of initial permeability, (μ'_i) increases with increasing Li content in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$. It is also observed that μ'_i for each sample increases with sintering temperatures because of uniform grain growth. The μ'_i remains fairly constant in the frequency range up to some critical frequency which is called resonance frequency, f_r . It is also observed that higher the μ'_i lower the f_r of the material. This confirms with Snoek's limit. The relative quality factor (Q) increases with increasing sintering temperature. Among all the studied samples, highest value of Q-factor (2165) is observed for $x=0.40$ sintered at 1300°C.

CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	IV
ABSTRACT	VI
CONTENTS	VIII
LIST OF FIGURES	X
LIST OF TABLES	XIII
LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS	XIV

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION 1-5

1.1	Introduction	1
1.2	Objectives of the Present Work	2
1.3	Summary of the Thesis	3

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW 6- 41

2.1	Overview of the Materials	6
2.2	Magnetic Ordering	9
2.3	Crystal Structure of Spinel Ferrites	12
2.4	Cation Distribution of Spinel Ferrites	14
2.5	Interaction Between Magnetic Moments on Lattice Sites	16
2.6	Magnetism in Spinel Ferrite	18
2.6.1	Exchange Interactions in Spinel	19
2.6.2	Néel Theory of Ferrimagnetism	23
2.6.3	Effect of Zinc Substitution on the Magnetic Moments in Spinel Ferrites	27
2.7	Microstructure	31
2.8	Theories of Permeability	33
2.8.1	Mechanisms of Permeability	35

2.8.1.1 Wall Permeability	36
2.8.1.2 Rotational Permeability	37

CHAPTER 3
EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

42-56

3.1	Composition of the studied ferrite system	42
3.2	Sample preparation	42
3.3	Combustion Method	43
3.4	Preparation of the Present Samples	47
3.5	X-ray Diffraction	48
3.6	Study of Microstructure	50
3.7	Average particle size measurement	50
3.8	Complex Permeability Measurement	53
	3.8.1 Techniques for the Permeability Measurement	53
	3.8.2 Frequency Characteristics of the Present Samples	54

CHAPTER 4
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

57-78

4.	Investigation of polycrystalline $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$	57
4.1	Structural analysis	57
4.1.1	X-ray diffraction analysis	57
4.1.2	Lattice constant	59
4.1.3	Average particle size	60
4.1.4	Density and porosity	61
4.2	Microstructures	62
4.3	Complex permeability	68

CHAPTER 5
CONCLUSIONS

77-78

5.1	Conclusions	77
5.2	Suggestions for future work	78

LIST OF FIGURES

	Pages
Figure 2.1. Temperature dependence of the inverse susceptibility for: (a) a diamagnetic material; (b) a paramagnetic material, showing Curie's law behaviour; (c) a ferromagnetic material, showing a spontaneous magnetization for $T < T_C$ and Curie-Weiss behaviour for $T > T_C$; (d) an antiferromagnetic material; (e) a ferrimagnetic material, showing a net spontaneous magnetization for $T < T_C$ and non linear behaviour for $T > T_C$.	11
Figure 2.2. Two subcells of a unit cell of the spinel structure.	13
Figure 2.3. Unit cell of spinel ferrite divided into eight subcells with <i>A</i> and <i>B</i> sites.	13
Figure 2.4. Nearest neighbours of (a) a tetrahedral site, (b) an octahedral site and (c) an anion site.	17
Figure 2.5. Interionic angles in the spinel structure for the different type of lattice site interactions.	17
Figure 2.6. Electronic configuration of atoms and ions.	19
Figure 2.7. Illustrating superexchange in <i>MnO</i> .	22
Figure 2.8. Schematic representation of the superexchange interaction in the magnetic oxides. The <i>p</i> orbital of an anion (center) interact with the <i>d</i> orbitals of the transitional metal cations.	22

Figure 2.9.	The temperature dependence of the inverse susceptibility for ferrimagnets.	25
Figure 2.10.	Superposition of various combinations of two opposing sublattice magnetizations producing differing resultants including one with a compensation point (schematic).	26
Figure 2.11.	Variation of magnetic moment (in Bohr magnetons per formula unit) with increasing zinc substitution.	29
Figure 2.12.	Schematic representation of spin arrangements in $Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$: (a) ferrimagnetic (for $x \leq 0.5$); (b) triangular or Yafet-Kittel (for $x > 0.5$); and (c) antiferromagnetic for $x \approx 1$.	30
Figure 2.13.	Porosity character: (a) intergranular, (b) intragranular.	32
Figure 2.14.	Grain growth (a) discontinuous, (b) duplex (schematic).	33
Figure 2.15.	Schematic magnetization curve showing the important parameter: initial permeability, μ_i (the slope of the curve at low fields) and the main magnetization mechanism in each magnetization range.	35
Figure 2.16.	Magnetization by wall motion and spin rotation.	37
Figure 3.1.	Flow chart of the stages in preparation of spinel ferrite.	44
Figure 3.2.	Schematic representation of sintering stages: (a) greenbody, (b) initial stage, (c) intermediate stage, and (d) final stage.	46
Figure 3.3.	Bragg law of diffraction.	48

Figure 3.4	Effect of fine particle size on diffraction curves (Schematic): (a). small particle size and (b) large particle size	51
Figure 4.1.	The X-ray diffraction patterns for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$	58
Figure 4.2.	The variation of lattice constant, a , calculated from each plane with $F(\theta)$ for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$.	59
Figure 4.3.	The variation of Lattice parameter with Mn content, x , for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$	60
Figure 4.4.	The optical micrographs of various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ compositions sintered at temperatures 1200 °C	61
Figure4.5.	The variation of density and porosity with Mn content for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at (a) 1200°C, (b) 1250°C (c) 1300°C, and (d) 1350°C	64 17
Fig. 4.6.	The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1250°C	65
Fig. 4.7.	The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1300°C	66
Fig. 4.8.	The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_{0.4}\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.08}\text{Fe}_{2.40}\text{O}_4$ sintered at different temperatures.	67 22
Fig.4.9:	The μ_i' and μ_i'' for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at (a) 1200, (b) 1250 and (c) 1300°C in air.	69
Fig.4.10:	The μ_i' and grain size for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1200°C in air.	70
Fig.4.11:	The μ_i' with Li content for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$. sintered at 1200°C in air.	70

Fig. 4.12. Loss factor as a function of frequency with Li content sintered at (a) 73 1200°C, (b) 1250°C and (c) 1300°C.

Fig. 4.13: The variation of relative quality factor with frequency for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$. Samples sintered at (a) 1200 °C and (b) 1250 °C (c) 1300 °C 74

LIST OF TABLES

	Pages
Table 4.1. The lattice parameter, density, porosity, average grain size and natural resonance frequency of the various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ samples sintered at different temperatures with fixed dwell time 1h.	63
Table 4.2. Particle size and FWHM of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ samples sintered at 1200°C.	68

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Alternating current
B	Magnetic induction
$F(\theta)$	Nelson-Riley function
f_r	Resonance frequency
g	Landé splitting factor
H_{cr}	Critical field
J	Exchange integral
K	Total anisotropy
K_I	Magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant
L_s	Self-inductance of the sample core
L_o	Inductance of the winding coil without sample
N_A	Avogadro's number
P	Porosity
P_{intra}	Intragranular porosity
P_{inter}	Intergranular porosity
P_e	Eddy-current loss
Q	Relative quality factor
T_c	Curie temperature
T_N	Néel temperature
T_s	Sintering temperature
$\tan \delta$	Loss factor
Z	Complex impedance
θ	Bragg's angle
γ	Domain wall energy
ω	Angular velocity
δ_w	Domain wall thickness
μ'	Real part of complex permeability
μ''	Imaginary part of complex permeability
μ_B	Bohr magneton
χ_{spin}	Intrinsic rotational susceptibility
χ_w	Domain wall susceptibility

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Ferrites possess the combined properties of magnetic materials and insulators. They form a complex system composed of grains, grain boundaries and pores. A ferrimagnetic material is defined as one which below a transition temperature exhibits a spontaneous magnetization that arises from non parallel arrangement of the strongly coupled magnetic moments. Most modern soft ferrites have spinel type crystal structure. It has tetrahedral A-site and octahedral B-site in AB_2O_4 crystal structure. It shows various magnetic properties depending on the the compositions and cation distribution. Various cations be placed in A site and B site to tune its magnetic properties. Depending on A site and B site cations it can exhibits ferromagnetic, antiferromagnetic spin (cluster) glass and paramagnetic behaviour [1]. The general chemical formula of such ferrites is $MeFe_2O_4$, where Me represents one or several of the divalent transition metals. These types of ferrites are subjects of intense theoretical and experimental investigation due to their remarkable magnetic and electric properties [2-7].

Spinel ferrites display improved properties by virtue of their unique electronic and crystalline structure which may be harnessed for various applications such as inductors, transformers, antennas, deflection yokes, choke coils, recording heads, electromagnetic interference (EMI) and power transformer [1, 8-12]. The Mn-Zn ferrites adequately suit these demands [13]. But for high performance, permeability and resistivity of these materials need to be increased. An important parameter for high performance is small grain size [14-15]. The core loss, consisting of hysteresis loss, eddy current loss and residual loss vary considerably with operating frequency and magnetic flux density. These

losses can be reduced by production of material with uniform microstructure. This type of material facilitates better domain wall movements, as they are free from lattice defects, pores and impurities. The factors responsible for controlling the grain size of the material are the method of preparation and conditions during preparation [16].

Recently, in our laboratory, Hossain *et. al* [17] have studied grain size dependent permeability of $\text{Ni}_{0.5-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ferrites prepared by the standard solid state reaction technique. It was reported that preparation condition of the samples and substitutions of Mn have an influence on the magnetic properties of these ferrites. In the present research, Mn has been substituted by Li in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$, and intend to investigate structural and magnetic properties of various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ prepared by combustion technique.

1.2 Objectives with specific aims

Ferrites are especially convenient for high frequency uses because of their high resistivity. The high frequency response of the complex permeability is therefore very useful in determining the convenient frequency range in which a particular ferrite material can be used. The mechanism of eddy current losses and damping of domain wall motion can be understood from the relative magnitudes of the real and imaginary parts of the complex permeability. The effect of composition and microstructure on the frequency response is therefore very useful.

The main objectives of the present research are as follows:

- Preparation of various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.00$ to 0.44 in the step of 0.10) nanocrystalline compositions by combustion technique. Various samples prepared from these powders have been sintered at different temperatures.

- Structural characterization was performed by X-ray diffraction (XRD). From the XRD results density and porosity of all compositions has been determined.
- From the microstructural analysis, the average grain size of all compositions has been studied.
- The complex initial permeability, μ_i , as a function of frequency (100Hz-120MHz) of each composition has been measured with Wayne Kerr Electronics Precision impedance analyzer.

1.3 Summary of the thesis

The format of the thesis is as follows:

Chapter 1 of this thesis deals with the introduction and importance of ferrites and objectives of the present work.

Chapter 2 gives a brief overview of the materials, theoretical background as well as crystal structure of the spinel type ferrites.

Chapter 3 gives the details of the sample preparation.

Chapter 4 gives the descriptions of different measurements that have been used in this research work.

Chapter 5 is devoted to the results of various investigations of the study and explanation of results in the light of existing theories.

The conclusions drawn from the overall experimental results and discussion are presented in Chapter 6.

References

- [1] Akther Hossain, A. K. M., Mahmud, S.T., Seki, M., Kawai, T., Tabata, H., “Structural, electrical transport, and magnetic properties of $\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ”, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.*, Vol-312, pp 210-219, 2007.
- [2] Leung, L. K., Evans, B. J., and Morrish, A. H., “Low-temperature Mössbauer study of a nickel-zinc ferrites.” *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol-8, pp 1273, 2004.
- [3] Schiessl, W., Potzel, W., Kerzel, H., Steiner, M. and Kalvius, G. M., “Magnetic properties of the ZnFe_2O_4 spinel,” *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol-53, pp 9143, 1996.
- [4] Hasting, J. M. and corliss, L. M., “An antiferromagnetic transition in zinc ferrite” *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol. 102, pp 1460, 1956
- [5] Hasting, J. M. and corliss, L. M.; “Neutron diffraction studies of zinc ferrite ad nickel ferrite”, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, Vol-15, pp 114, 1953
- [6] Valenzuela, R; *Magnetic Ceramic*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1994
- [7] Golman, A., *handbook of Modern ferromagnetic Materials*, Kulwer Acad. Pub, Boston, U. S. A. 1999.
- [8] Son, S., Taheri, M., Carpenter, E., Harris, V. G., McHenry, M. E., “Synthesis of ferrite and nickel ferrite nanoparticles using radio-frequency thermal plasma torch”, *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol-91, pp 7589, 2002.
- [9] Fannin, P. C., Slawska-Waniewska, A., Didukh, P., Giannitoics, A., Charles, S. W; “Preparation of nanocrystalline MnFe_2O_4 by doping with Ti^{4+} ions using solid-state reaction route”, *Eur. Phys. J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol-17, pp 3, 2002.
- [10] Sousa, M. H; Tourinho, F. A; Depeyrot, J; Da silva, G. J; Lara, M. C. F; “New Electric Double-Layered Magnetic Fluids Based on Copper, Nickel, and Zinc Ferrite Nanostructures”, *J. Phys. Chem.*, Vol-105, pp 1169, 2001.
- [11] Akther Hossain, A. K. M., Seki, M., Kawai, T., Tabata, H., “Colossal magnetoresistance in spinel type $\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Ni}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ”, *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol-96, pp 1273- 1275, 2004.
- [12] Akther Hossain, A.K.M., Tabata, H., Kawai, T., “Magnetoresistive properties of $\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ferrites”, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.*, Vol-320, pp 1157, 2008.

- [13] Keluskar, S. H; Tangsali, R. B; Naik, G. K; Budkuley, J. S; “High permeability of low loss Mn-Zn ferrite obtained by sintering nanoparticle Mn-Zn ferrite”, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.*, Vol-305, pp 296-303, 2006.
- [14] Znidarsic, M. A; Zajc, I; “High resistivity grain boundaries in doped MnZn ferrites for high frequency power supplies”, *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol-82, pp 333, 1997.
- [15] Inaba, H., Abe, T., Kitano, Y., Shimomura, J., “Mechanism of core loss and the Grain-boundary structure of Niobium-Doped Manganese –Zinc Ferrite”, *J. Solid State Chem.*, Vol-121, pp 117, 1996.
- [16] Verma, A., Goel, T.C., Mendiratta, R. G., “Low temperature processing of Ni-Zn ferrite by citrate precursor method and study of properties”, *Mater. Sci. Tech.*, Vol. 16, pp 712, 2000.
- [17] Akther Hossain, A. K. M., Biswas, T. S., Mahmud, S. T., Yanagida, T., Tanaka, H., Kawai, T., “Enhancement of initial permeability due to Mn substitution in polycrystalline $\text{Ni}_{0.5-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ”, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.*, Vol-321, pp 81-87, 2009.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Double oxides of iron and other metals are important members of ferrimagnetic system commonly known as ferrites. The outstanding properties of ferrites are their complex magnetic structure, which can be varied to tailor their magnetic properties for various high frequency applications. In this chapter we describe a brief overview of the ferrites. The basic issue of ferrimagnetism, crystal structure of the spinel ferrites and effect of non-magnetic Li substitution on the magnetic moments in spinel ferrites are discussed. A few theoretical aspects of complex permeability are also discussed.

2.1 Overview of the Materials

Ferrites commonly expressed by the general chemical formula $MeO.Fe_2O_3$, where Me represents divalent metals, first commanded the public attention when Hilpert (1909) focused on the usefulness of ferrites at high frequency [1]. A systematic investigation was launched by Snoek (1936) at Philips Research Laboratory [2]. At the same time Takai (1937) in Japan was seriously engaged in the research work on the same materials [1]. Snoek's extensive works on ferrites unveiled many mysteries regarding magnetic properties of ferrites. He was particularly looking for high permeability materials of cubic structure. This particular structure for symmetry reasons supports low crystalline anisotropy. He found suitable materials in the form of mixed spinels of the type $MeZnFe_2O_4$, where Me stands for metals like Cu , Mg , Ni or Mn , for which permeability were found to be up to 4000 [1-3]. Here after starts the story of $Ni-Zn$ ferrites. Remarkable properties like high permeability, low loss factor, high stability of permeability with temperature and time, high wear resistance, controlled coercive force, low switching coefficient etc. have aptly placed $Ni-Zn$ ferrites as highly demandable ferrites to both researchers and manufacturers. Every year great deals of paper are being

published on various aspects of *Ni-Zn* ferrites. A large number of scientists and technologists are engaged in research to bring about improvements on the magnetic properties of *Ni-Zn* ferrites.

The sintering process is considered to be one of the most vital steps in ferrite preparation and often plays a dominant role in many magnetic properties. Tasaki *et al.* [4] studied the effect of sintering atmosphere on permeability of sintered ferrite. They found that high density is one of the factors, which contribute to greater permeability. However, permeability decreased in an atmosphere without O_2 at high sintering temperature where high density was expected. This decrease in permeability is attributed to the variation of chemical composition caused by volatilization of *Zn*. At low sintering temperature a high permeability is obtained in an atmosphere without O_2 because densification and stoichiometry plays a principal role in increasing permeability. At high sintering temperature the highest permeability is obtained in the presence of O_2 because the effect of decrease of *Zn* content can then be neglected.

Studying the electromagnetic properties of ferrites, Nakamura [5] suggested that both the sintering density and the average grain size increased with sintering temperature. These changes were responsible for variations in magnetization, initial permeability and electrical resistivity.

High permeability attainment is certainly affected by the microstructure of the ferrites. Roess showed that [6] the very high permeability is restricted to certain temperature ranges and the shapes of permeability versus temperature curves are strongly affected by any inhomogeneity in the ferrite structure.

Hoque *et. al.* [7] studied Cu substituted Li-ferrite and observed that, the structural properties are strongly dependent on the sintering temperature due to the Jahn-Teller

distortion of Cu^{2+} . An increase in initial permeability has been observed with the increase in Cu content but the resonance frequency shifts towards the lower frequency. In recent years, magnetic, electrical, and microstructure properties of manganese and cadmium co-substituted lithium ferrite has been studied by Verma et al. [8]. This work infer that, a small amount of substitution in manganese in $\text{Li}_{0.35}\text{Cd}_{0.35}\text{Mn}_x\text{Fe}_{2.35-x}\text{O}_4$ series can improves its permeability, Dc resistivity and microstructure properties which are very essential in microwave and power applications.

Rezlescu *et al.* [9] reported that the sintering behaviour and microstructure of the ferrites samples largely affected by *PbO* addition. *PbO* significantly reduced the sintering temperatures, thus energy consumption is minimized and material loss by evaporation is minimized [10].

There are two mechanisms in the phenomenon of permeability; spin rotation in the magnetic domains and wall displacements. The uncertainty of contribution from each of the mechanisms makes the interpretation of the experimental results difficult. Globus [11] shows that the intrinsic rotational permeability μ_r and 180° wall permeability μ_w may be written as: $\mu_r = 1 + 2\pi M_s^2 / K$ and $\mu_w = 1 + 3\pi M_s^2 D / 4\gamma$, where M_s is the saturation magnetization, K is the total anisotropy, D is the grain diameter and $\gamma \equiv K\delta_w$ is the wall energy.

Rosales *et al.* [12] measured the complex permeability of $\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Ni}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ferrites with $0.3 \leq x \leq 0.4$. They show that the relaxation frequency and magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant is related by the equation: $f_x = f_{x0} + AK_1$, where f_{x0} and A are constants.

El-Shabasy [13] studied the DC electrical resistivity of $\text{Zn}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ferrites. He shows that the ferrite samples have semiconductor behaviour where DC electrical

resistivity decreases on increasing the temperature. $\rho(T)$ for all samples follows $\rho(T) = \rho_0 \exp(E/k_B T)$, where E is the activation energy for electric conduction and ρ_0 is the pre-exponential constant or resistivity at infinitely high temperature. The DC resistivity, $\rho(T)$, decreases as the Zn ion substitution increases. It is reported that Zn ions prefer the occupation of tetrahedral (A) sites, Ni ions prefer the occupation of octahedral (B) sites while Fe ions partially occupy the A and B sites. On increasing Zn substitution (at A sites), the Ni ion concentration (at B sites) will decrease. This lead to the migration of some Fe ions from A sites to B sites to substitute the reduction in Ni ion concentration at B sites. As a result, the number of ferrous and ferric ions at B sites (which is responsible for electric conduction in ferrites) increases. Consequently ρ decreases on Zn substitution. Another reason for the decrease in ρ on increasing Zn ion substitution is that, zinc is less resistive ($\rho = 5.92 \mu\Omega cm$) than nickel ($\rho = 6.99 \mu\Omega cm$). The main conductivity mechanism in ferrites is attributed to electron hopping between Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} in octahedral sites. Resistivity in spinels is very sensitive to stoichiometry; a small variation of Fe content in $Zn_{0.7}Ni_{0.3}Fe_{2+x}O_{4-y}$ results in resistivity variations of $\sim 10^7$. Excess Fe can easily dissolve in spinel phase by a partial reduction of Fe from $3Fe_2^{3+}O_3$ to $2Fe^{2+}Fe_2^{3+}O_4$ (and $1/2O_2 \uparrow$)[2].

2.2 Magnetic Ordering

The onset of magnetic order in solids has two basic requirements:

- (i) Individual atoms should have magnetic moments (spins),
- (ii) Exchange interactions should exist that couple them together.

Magnetic moments originate in solids as a consequence of overlapping of the electronic wave function with those of neighboring atoms. This condition is best fulfilled by some

transition metals and rare-earths. The exchange interactions depend sensitively upon the inter-atomic distance and the nature of the chemical bonds, particularly of nearest neighbour atoms. When the positive exchange dominates, which corresponds to parallel coupling of neighbouring atomic moments (spins), the magnetic system becomes ferromagnetic below a certain temperature T_C called the Curie temperature. The common spin directions are determined by the minimum of magneto-crystalline anisotropy energy of the crystal. Therefore, ferromagnetic substances are characterized by spontaneous magnetization. But a ferromagnetic material in the demagnetized state displays no net magnetization in zero field because in the demagnetized state a ferromagnetic of macroscopic size is divided into a number of small regions called domains, spontaneously magnetized to saturation value and the directions of these spontaneous magnetization of the various domains are such that the net magnetization of the specimen is zero. The existence of domains is a consequence of energy minimization. The size and formation of these domains is in a complicated manner dependent on the shape of the specimen as well as its magnetic and thermal history. When negative exchange dominates, adjacent atomic moments (spins) align antiparallel to each other, and the substance is said to be anti-ferromagnetic below a characteristic temperature, T_N , called the Néel temperature. In the simplest case, the lattice of an anti-ferromagnet is divided into two sublattices with the magnetic moments of these in anti-parallel alignment. This result is zero net magnetization. A special case of anti-ferromagnetism is ferrimagnetism. In ferrimagnetism, there are also two sublattices with magnetic moments in opposite directions, but the magnetization of the sublattices are of unequal strength resulting in a non-zero magnetization and therefore has net spontaneous magnetization. At the macroscopic level of domain structures, ferromagnetic and ferrimagnetic materials are therefore similar.

Figure 2.1. Temperature dependence of the inverse susceptibility for: (a) a diamagnetic material; (b) a paramagnetic material, showing Curie's law behaviour; (c) a ferromagnetic material, showing a spontaneous magnetization for $T < T_c$ and Curie-Weiss behaviour for $T > T_c$; (d) an antiferromagnetic material; (e) a ferrimagnetic material, showing a net spontaneous magnetization for $T < T_c$ and non linear behaviour for $T > T_c$.

The Curie and Néel temperatures characterize a phase transition between the magnetically ordered and disordered (paramagnetic) states. From these simple cases of magnetic ordering various types of magnetic order exists, particularly in metallic substances. Because of long-range order and oscillatory nature of the exchange interaction,

mediated by the conduction electrons, structures like helical, conical and modulated patterns might occur. A useful property for characterizing the magnetic materials is the magnetic susceptibility, χ , defined as the magnetization, M , divided by the applied magnetic field, H i.e. $\chi = M / H$. The temperature dependence of susceptibility or, more accurately, inverse of susceptibility is a good characterization parameter for magnetic materials, Fig. 2.1. Fig. 2.1(e) shows that in the paramagnetic region, the variation of the inverse susceptibility with temperature of a ferrite material is decidedly non-linear. Thus the ferrite materials do not obey the Curie-Weiss law, $\chi = C / (T - T_C)$ [2, 15].

2.3 Crystal Structure of Spinel Ferrites

Ferrites have the cubic structure, which is very close to that of the mineral spinel $MgO.Al_2O_3$, and are called cubic spinel. Analogous to the mineral spinel, magnetic spinel have the general formula $MeO.Fe_2O_3$ or $MeFe_2O_4$ where Me is the divalent metal ion [16]. This crystal structure was first determined by Bragg and by Nishikawa [1,15]. Formerly, spinels containing Fe were called ferrites but now the term has been broadened to include many other ferrimagnets including garnets and hexagonal ferrites these need not necessarily contain iron. The spinel lattice is composed of a close-packed oxygen (radius about 1.3\AA) arrangement in which 32 oxygen ions form a unit cell that is the smallest repeating unit in the crystal network. The unit cell of the ideal spinel structures is given in Fig. 2.2. Between the layers of oxygen ions, if we simply visualize them as spheres, there are interstices that may accommodate the metal ions (radii ranging from 0.6 to 0.8\AA). Now, the interstices are not all the same: some which we call A sites are surrounded by or coordinated with 4 nearest neighboring oxygen ions whose lines connecting their centers form a tetrahedron. Thus, A sites are called tetrahedral sites. The other type of sites (B sites) is coordinated by 6 nearest neighbor oxygen ions whose center connecting lines

describe an octahedron. The B sites are called octahedral sites. In the unit cell of 32 oxygen ions there are 64 tetrahedral sites and 32 octahedral sites. If all these were filled with metal ions, of either +2 or +3 valence, the positive charge would be very much greater than the negative charge and so the structure would not be electrically neutral. It turns out that of the 64 tetrahedral sites, only 8 are occupied and out of 32 octahedral sites, only 16 are occupied. Thus the unit cell contains eight formula units AB_2O_4 , with 8 A sites, 16 B sites and 32 oxygen ions, and total of $8 \times 7 = 56$ ions. A spinel unit cell contains two types of subcells, Fig. 2.2.

The two types of subcells alternate in a three-dimensional array so that each fully repeating unit cell requires eight subcells, Fig. 2.3.

Figure 2.2. Two subcells of a unit cell of the spinel structure.

Figure 2.3. Unit cell of spinel ferrite divided into eight sub cells with A and B sites.

The positions of the ions in the spinel lattice are not perfectly regular (as the packing of hard spheres) and some distortion does occur. The tetrahedral sites are

often too small for the metal ions so that the oxygen ions move slightly to accommodate them. The oxygen ions connected with the octahedral sites move in such a way as to shrink the size the octahedral cell by the same amount as the tetrahedral site expands. The movement of the tetrahedral oxygen is reflected in a quantity called the oxygen parameter, which is the distance between the oxygen ion and the face of the cube edge along the cube diagonal of the spinel subcell. This distance is theoretically equal to $3/8a_0$ where a_0 is the lattice constant [1].

2.4 Cation Distribution of Spinel Ferrites

In spinel structure the distribution of cations over the tetrahedral or *A* sites and octahedral or *B* sites can be present in a variety of ways. If all the Me^{2+} ions in $Me^{2+}Me_2^{3+}O_4$ are in tetrahedral and all Me^{3+} ions in octahedral positions, the spinel is then called normal spinel. Another cation distribution in spinel exists, where one half of the cations Me^{3+} are in the *A* positions and the rest, together with the Me^{2+} ions are randomly distributed among the *B* positions. The spinel having the latter kind of cation distribution is known as inverse spinel. The distribution of these spinels can be summarized as [2, 17-18]:

- 1) Normal spinels, i.e. the divalent metal ions are on *A*-sites: $Me^{2+}[Me_2^{3+}]O_4$,
- 2) Inverse spinels, i.e. the divalent metal ions are on *B*-sites: $Me^{3+}[Me^{2+}Me_2^{3+}]O_4$.

A completely normal or inverse spinel represents the extreme cases. *Zn* ferrites have normal spinel structure and its formula may be written as $Zn^{2+}[Fe^{3+}Fe^{3+}]O_4^{2-}$. On the other hand, *Ni* ferrites have inverse spinel structure and its formula may be written as $Fe^{3+}[Ni^{2+}Fe^{3+}]O_4^{2-}$. There are many spinel oxides which have cation distributions intermediate between these two extreme cases and are called mixed spinels. The general

cation distribution for the spinel can be indicated as:

where the first and third brackets represent the A and B sites respectively. For normal spinel $x=1$, for inverse spinel $x=0$. The quantity x is a measure of the degree of inversion. In the case of some spinel oxides x depends upon the method of preparation.

The basic magnetic properties of the ferrites are very sensitive functions of their cation distributions. Mixed ferrites having interesting and useful magnetic properties are prepared by mixing two or more different types of metal ions. The chemical formula of mixed *Ni-Zn* ferrite may be written as $(Zn_x^{2+} Fe_{1-x}^{3+})[Ni_{1-x}^{2+} Fe_{1+x}^{3+}]O_4^{2-}$ where $0 \leq x \leq 1$.

Spinel oxides are ionic compounds and hence the chemical bonding occurring in them can be taken as purely ionic to a good approximation. The total energy involved, however, consists of the Coulomb energy, the Born repulsive energy, the polarization and the magnetic interaction energy. The energy terms are all dependent on lattice constant, oxygen position parameter and the ionic distribution. In principle the equilibrium cation distribution can be calculated by minimizing the total energy with respect to these variables. But the only energy that can be written with any accuracy is the Coulomb energy. The individual preference of some ions for certain sites resulting from their electronic configuration also play an important role. The divalent ions are generally larger than the trivalent (because the larger charge produces greater electrostatic attraction and so pulls the outer orbits inward). The octahedral sites are also larger than the tetrahedral. Therefore, it would be reasonable that the trivalent ions Fe^{3+} (0.67Å) would go into the tetrahedral sites and the divalent ions Fe^{2+} (0.83Å) go into the octahedral. Two exceptions are found in Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} which prefer tetrahedral sites because the electronic configuration is favourable for tetrahedral bonding to the oxygen ions. Thus Zn^{2+} (0.82Å)

prefer tetrahedral sites over the Fe^{3+} (0.67Å) ions. Zn^{2+} and Co^{2+} have same ionic radius but Zn prefers tetrahedral sites and Co prefers octahedral sites because of the configuration exception. Ni^{2+} (0.78Å) and Cr^{3+} (0.64Å) have strong preferences for octahedral sites. Hence the factors influencing the distribution of cations among the two possible lattice sites are mainly their ionic radii of the specific ions, the size of the interstices, temperature, the matching of their electronic configuration to the surrounding anions and the electrostatic energy of the lattice, the so-called Madelung energy, which has the predominant contribution to the lattice energy under the constrain of overall energy minimization and charge neutrality.

2.5 Interaction between Magnetic Moments on Lattice Sites

Spontaneous magnetization of spinels (at 0K) can be estimated on the basis of their composition, cation distribution, and the relative strength of the possible interaction. Since cation-cation distances are generally large, direct (ferromagnetic) interactions are negligible. Because of the geometry of orbital involved, the strongest superexchange interaction is expected to occur between octahedral and tetrahedral cations. The strength of interaction or exchange force between the moments of the two metal ions on different sites depends on the distances between these ions and the oxygen ion that links them and also on the angle between the three ions. The nearest neighbours of a tetrahedral, an octahedral and an anion site are shown in Fig. 2.4. The interaction is greatest for an angle of 180° and also where the interionic distances are the shortest. Fig. 2.5 shows the interionic distances and the angles between the ions for the different type of interactions. In the *A-A* and *B-B* cases, the angles are too small or the distances between the metal ions and the oxygen ions are too large. The best combination of distances and angles are found in *A-B* interactions.

Figure 2.4. Nearest neighbours of (a) a tetrahedral site, (b) an octahedral site and (c) an anion site.

Figure 2.5. Interionic angles in the spinel structure for the different type of lattice site interactions.

For an undistorted spinel, the $A-O-B$ angles are about 125° and 154° [1-2, 19]. The $B-O-B$ angles are 90° and 125° but the latter, one of the $B-B$ distances is large. In the $A-A$ case the angle is about 80° . Therefore, the interaction between moments on the A and B site is strongest. The BB interaction is much weaker and the most unfavorable situation occurs in the AA interaction. By examining the interaction involving the major contributor, or the $A-B$ interaction which orients the unpaired spins of these ions antiparallel, Néel was able to explain the ferrimagnetism of ferrites.

2.6 Magnetism in Spinel Ferrite

The magnetic moment of a free atom is associated with the orbital and spin motions of electrons in an incomplete sub-shell of the electronic structure of the atom. In crystals the orbital motions are quenched, that is the orbital planes may be considered to be fixed in space relative to the crystal lattice, and in such a way that in bulk the crystal has no resultant moment from this source. Moreover this orbital-lattice coupling is so strong that the application of a magnetic field has little effect upon it. The spin axes are not tightly bound to the lattice as are the orbital axes. The anions surrounding a magnetic cation subject it to a strong inhomogeneous electric field and influence the orbital angular momentum. However, the spin angular momentum remains unaffected. For the first transition group elements this crystal field effect is intense partly due to the large radius of the 3d shell and partly due to the lack of any outer electronic shell to screen the 3d shell whose unpaired electrons only contribute to the magnetic moment. We have originally defined the magnetic moment in connection with permanent magnets. The electron itself may well be called the smallest permanent magnet [1]. For an atom with a resultant spin quantum number S , the spin magnetic moment will be

$$\mu = g\sqrt{S(S+1)}\mu_B$$

Where g is the Landé splitting factor and μ_B , known as the Bohr magneton, is the fundamental unit of magnetic moment. The value of g for pure spin moment is 2 and the quantum number associated with each electron spin is $\pm 1/2$. The direction of the moment is comparable to the direction of the magnetization (from South to North poles) of a permanent

Figure 2.6. Electronic configuration of atoms and ions

magnet to which the electron is equivalent. Fig. 2.6 illustrates the electronic configuration of Fe atoms and Fe^{3+} ions. Fe atom has four unpaired electrons and Fe^{3+} ion has five unpaired electrons. Each unpaired electron spin produced 1 Bohr magneton. In compounds, ions and molecules, account must be taken of the electrons used for bonding or transferred in ionization. It is the number of unpaired electrons remaining after these processes occur that gives the net magnetic moment [1]. According to the Hund's rules the moment of Fe atom and Fe^{3+} ion are $4\mu_B$ and $5\mu_B$ respectively. Similarly the moment of Fe^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ion are $4\mu_B$ and $2\mu_B$ respectively.

2.6.1 Exchange Interactions in Spinel

The intense short-range electrostatic field, which is responsible for the magnetic ordering, is the exchange force that is quantum mechanical in origin and is related to the overlapping of total wave functions of the neighbouring atoms. The total wave function consists of the orbital and spin motions. Usually the net quantum number is written as S , because the magnetic moments arise mostly due to the spin motion as described above. The exchange interactions coupling the spins of a pair of electrons are proportional to the scalar product of their spin vectors [16, 18, 20],

$$V_{ij} = -2J_{ij} \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \quad (2.1)$$

where J_{ij} is the exchange integral given in a self explanatory notation by

$$J_{ij} = \int \psi_i^*(1)\psi_j^*(2) \left[\frac{1}{r_{12}} + \frac{1}{r_{ij}} - \frac{1}{r_{i1}} - \frac{1}{r_{j2}} \right] \psi_i(2)\psi_j(1) dv_1 dv_2 \quad (2.2)$$

In this expression r 's are the distances, subscripts i and j refer to the atoms, 1 and 2 refers to the two electrons. If the J in equation (2.1) is positive, we achieve ferromagnetism. A negative J may give rise to anti-ferromagnetism or ferrimagnetism.

Magnetic interactions in spinel ferrites as well as in some ionic compounds are different from the one considered above because the cations are mutually separated by bigger anions (oxygen ions). These anions obscure the direct overlapping of the cation charge distributions, sometimes partially and some times completely making the direct exchange interaction very weak. Cations are too far apart in most oxides for a direct cation-cation interaction. Instead, superexchange interactions appear, i.e., indirect exchange via anion p -orbitals that may be strong enough to order the magnetic moments. Apart from the electronic structure of cations this type of interactions strongly depends on the geometry of arrangement of the two interacting cations and the intervening anion. Both the distance and the angles are relevant. Usually only the interactions with in first coordination sphere (when both the cations are in contact with the anion) are important. In the Néel theory of ferrimagnetism the interactions taken as effective are inter- and intra-sublattice interactions A - B , A - A and B - B . The type of magnetic order depends on their relative strength.

The superexchange mechanism between cations that operate via the intermediate anions was proposed by Kramer for such cases and was developed by Anderson and Van Vleck [17, 18]. A simple example of superexchange is provided by MnO which was chosen by Anderson. From the crystal structure of MnO it will be seen that the antiparallel manganese ions are collinear with their neighbouring oxygen ions. The O^{2-} ions each have six $2p$ electrons in three antiparallel pairs. The outer electrons of the Mn^{2+} ions are in $3d$ sub-

shells which are half filled with five electrons in each. The phenomenon of superexchange is considered to be due to an overlap between the manganese $3d$ orbits and the oxygen $2p$ orbits with a continuous interchange of electrons between them. It appears that, for the overall energy of the system to be a minimum, the moments of the manganese ions on either side of the oxygen ion must be antiparallel. The manganese magnetic moments are thus, in effect, coupled through the intervening oxygen ion. The idea is illustrated in Fig. 2.7.

In Figs. 2.7(a) and 2.7(c) the outer electrons in a pair of Mn^{2+} ions, and in an intervening O^{2-} ion in the unexcited state, are shown by the arrows. One suggested mode of coupling is indicated in Fig. 2.7(b). The two electrons of a pair in the oxygen ion are simultaneously transferred, one to the left and the other to the right. If their directions of spin are unchanged then, by Hund's rules, the moments of the two manganese ions must be antiparallel as shown. Another possibility is represented in Fig. 2.7(d). One electron only has been transferred to the manganese ion on the left. The oxygen ion now has a moment of $1\mu_B$ and if there is negative interaction between the oxygen ion and the right-hand manganese ion then again the moments of the manganese ions will be antiparallel. If these ideas are accepted then the oxygen ions play an essential part in producing antiferromagnetism in the oxide. Moreover, because of the dumbbell shape of the $2p$ orbits, the coupling mechanism should be most effective when the metal ions and the oxygen ions lie in one straight line, that is, the angle between the bonds is 180° , and this is the case with MnO . In the case of spinel ferrites the coupling is of the indirect type which involves overlapping of oxygen wave functions with those of the neighboring cations. Consider two transition metal cations separated by an O , Fig. 2.8. The O^{2-} has no net magnetic moment since it has completely filled shells, with p -type outermost orbitals. Orbital p_x has two electrons: one with spin up, and the other with spin down, consistent with Pauli's exclusion principle.

Figure 2.7. Illustrating superexchange in MnO .

Figure 2.8. Schematic representation of the superexchange interaction in the magnetic oxides. The p orbital of an anion (center) interact with the d orbitals of the transitional metal cations.

The essential point is that when an oxygen p orbital overlaps with a cation d orbital, one of the p electrons can be accepted by the cations. When one of the transition-metal cations is brought close the O^{2-} , partial electron overlap (between a $3d$ electron from the cation and a $2p$ electron from the O^{2-}) can occur only for antiparallel spins, because electrons with the same spin are repelled. Empty $3d$ states in the cation are available for partial occupation by the O^{2-} electron, with an antiparallel orientation. Electron overlap between the other cation and the O^{2-} then occurs resulting in antiparallel spins and therefore antiparallel

order between the cations. Since the p orbitals are linear, the strongest interaction is expected to take place for $cation-O^{2-}-cation$ angles close to 180° [2].

2.6.2. Néel Theory of Ferrimagnetism

If we consider the simplest case of a two-sublattice system having antiparallel and non-equal magnetic moments, the inequality may be due to:

- 1) different elements in different sites,
- 2) same element in different ionic states, and
- 3) different crystalline fields leading to different effective moments for ions having the same spin.

The spins on one sublattice are under the influence of exchange forces due to the spins on the second sublattice as well as due to other spins on the same sublattice. The molecular fields acting on the two sublattices A and B can be written as [2, 15-20]

$$\vec{H}_A = \lambda_{AA}\vec{M}_A + \lambda_{AB}\vec{M}_B,$$

$$\vec{H}_B = \lambda_{AB}\vec{M}_A + \lambda_{BB}\vec{M}_B$$

where \vec{M}_A and \vec{M}_B are the magnetizations of the two sublattices and λ 's are the Weiss constants. Since the interaction between the sublattices is antiferromagnetic, λ_{AB} must be negative, but λ_{AA} and λ_{BB} may be negative or positive depending on the crystal structure and the nature of the interacting atoms. Probably, these interactions are also negative, though they are in general quite small.

Assuming all the exchange interactions to be negative the molecular fields will be then given by

$$\vec{H}_A = -\lambda_{AA}\vec{M}_A - \lambda_{AB}\vec{M}_B,$$

$$\vec{H}_B = -\lambda_{AB}\vec{M}_A - \lambda_{BB}\vec{M}_B$$

Since in general, λ_{AA} and λ_{BB} are small compared to λ_{AB} , it is convenient to express the strengths of these interactions relative to the dominant λ_{AB} interaction.

Let $\lambda_{AA} = \alpha\lambda_{AB}$

and $\lambda_{BB} = \beta\lambda_{AB}$

In an external applied field \vec{H} , the fields acting on A and B sites are

$$\vec{H}_A = \vec{H} - \lambda_{AB}(\alpha\vec{M}_A - \vec{M}_B),$$

$$\vec{H}_B = \vec{H} - \lambda_{AB}(\vec{M}_A - \beta\vec{M}_B)$$

At temperatures higher than the transition temperature, T_N , \vec{H}_A , \vec{M}_A and \vec{M}_B are all parallel and we can write

$$\vec{M}_A = \frac{C_A}{T}[\vec{H} - \lambda_{AB}(\alpha\vec{M}_A - \vec{M}_B)], \quad (2.3)$$

$$\vec{M}_B = \frac{C_B}{T}[\vec{H} - \lambda_{AB}(\vec{M}_A - \beta\vec{M}_B)] \quad (2.4)$$

where C_A and C_B are the Curie constants for the two sublattices.

$$C_A = N_A g \mu_B^2 S_A(S_A + 1)/3K$$

and $C_B = N_B g \mu_B^2 S_B(S_B + 1)/3K$

N_A and N_B denote the number of magnetic ions on A and B sites respectively and S_A and S_B are their spin quantum numbers. Solving for the susceptibility, χ , one gets [2, 15]

$$\frac{1}{\chi} = \frac{T}{C} - \frac{1}{\chi_0} - \frac{b}{T - \theta}$$

$$\frac{1}{\chi} = \frac{T + (C/\chi_0)}{C} - \frac{b}{T - \theta} \quad (2.5)$$

where C , χ_0 , b and θ are constants for particular substance and are given by

$$C = C_A + C_B$$

$$\frac{1}{\chi_0} = -\frac{1}{C^2} [C_A^2 \lambda_{AA} + C_B^2 \lambda_{BB} + 2C_A C_B \lambda_{AB}]$$

$$b = \frac{C_A C_B}{C^3} [C_A^2 (\lambda_{AA} - \lambda_{BB})^2 + C_B^2 (\lambda_{BB} - \lambda_{AB})^2 - 2C_A C_B \{ \lambda_{AB}^2 - (\lambda_{AA} + \lambda_{BB}) \lambda_{AB} + \lambda_{AA} \lambda_{BB} \}]$$

$$\theta = -\frac{C_A C_B}{C} (\lambda_{AB} + \lambda_{BB}) - 2\lambda_{AB}$$

Equation (2.5) represents a hyperbola, and the physically meaning part of it is plotted in Fig. 2.9. This curvature of the plot of $1/\chi$ versus T is a characteristics feature of a ferrimagnet. It cuts the temperature axis at T_c , called the Ferrimagnetic Curie point. At high temperatures the last term of equation (2.5) become negligible, and reduces to a Curie-Weiss law:

$$\chi = \frac{C}{T + (C/\chi_0)}$$

This is the equation of straight line, shown dashed in Fig. 2.9, to which the $1/\chi$ versus T curve becomes asymptotic at high temperatures.

Figure 2.9. The temperature dependence of the inverse susceptibility for ferrimagnets.

The Ferrimagnetic Curie temperature T_C is obtained from equations (2.3) and (2.4) with $H = 0$ and setting the determinant of the coefficients of M_i equal to zero. This gives

$$T_C = \frac{1}{2}[C_A\lambda_{AA} + C_B\lambda_{BB} + \{(C_A\lambda_{AA} - C_B\lambda_{BB})^2 + 4C_A C_B\lambda_{AB}^2\}^{1/2}] \quad (2.6)$$

Equation (2.5) is in good agreement with the experiment, except near the Curie point. The experimental Curie temperature, the temperature at which the susceptibility becomes infinite and spontaneous magnetization appears, is lower than the theoretical Curie temperature [15]. This disagreement between theory and experiment in the region of Curie point is presumably due to the short-range spin order (spin clusters) at temperatures above experimental T_C [2, 15].

Figure 2.10. Superposition of various combinations of two opposing sublattice magnetizations producing differing resultants including one with a compensation point (schematic).

The sublattice magnetizations will in general have different temperature dependences because the effective molecular fields acting on them are different. This suggests the possibility of having anomaly in the net magnetization versus temperature curves, Fig. 2.10. For most ferrimagnets the curve is similar to that of ferromagnets, but in a few cases there be a compensation point in the curve, Fig. 2.10(c) [1, 15]. At a point below the Curie temperature point, the two sublattice magnetizations are equal and thus appear to have no moment. This temperature is called the compensation point. Below this temperature one sublattice magnetization is larger and provides the net moment. Above this temperature the other magnetization does dominates and the net magnetization reverses direction.

The essential requisite for Néel configuration is a strong negative exchange interaction between A and B sublattices which results in their being magnetized in opposite directions below the transition point. But there may be cases where intrasublattice interactions are comparable with intersublattice interaction. Neel's theory predicts paramagnetism for such substances at all temperatures. This is unreasonable since strong AA or BB interaction may lead to some kind of ordering especially at low temperature. In the cases of no AB interaction, antiferromagnetic ordering may be expected either in the A or in the B sublattice. Under certain conditions there may be non-collinear spin arrays of still lower energy.

2.6.3 Effect of Zinc Substitution on the Magnetic Moments in Spinel Ferrites

Fe_3O_4 has ferromagnetic properties because of its inverse structure which leads to the formation of domains. A unit cell of Fe_3O_4 contains eight formula units each of which may be written in the form $Fe^{3+}[Fe^{2+}Fe^{3+}]O_4^{2-}$ [17]. Snoek and his co-workers found that oxides of inverse structure could be artificially produced in which the divalent ions of another element, for example Mn , Ni , Co , Mg or Cu , could be substituted for the divalent

Fe^{2+} ions in Fe_3O_4 . An extensive range of ferrites could thus be made having the general formula $Fe^{\rightarrow 3+}[M^{\leftarrow 2+} Fe^{\leftarrow 3+}]O_4^{2-}$, where arrows indicate spin ordering. Since the trivalent iron ions are equally distributed on A and B sites they cancel each other out magnetically, and the magnetic moment per formula unit is then theoretically the same as the magnetic moment of the divalent ion. The Ni ferrite has a moment of $2.3\mu_B$ compared with a theoretical value of $2\mu_B$ [1]. Zn ferrite is a normal spinel, with Zn^{2+} ($3d^{10}$) ions in A sites have zero magnetic moment; Fe^{3+} ions in B sites have a magnetic moment $5\mu_B$. The cation distribution can be written as $Zn^{2+}[Fe^{\rightarrow 3+} Fe^{\leftarrow 3+}]O_4$, where spin ordering is indicated by arrows. The zero magnetic moment of Zn^{2+} ions leaves trivalent iron ions on B sites with a negative BB interaction between equal ions. Therefore Zn ferrite is not ferromagnetic. Zinc ferrite therefore be expected to be antiferromagnetic and thus to have a Néel point, though measurements show it to be paramagnetic only [1-2, 15, 17].

Magnetic properties can be modified widely by cation substitution. An illustrative case is substitution of Ni by Zn in Ni ferrite to form solid solutions $Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$. The cation distribution can be written as $(Zn_x^{2+} Fe_{1-x}^{3+})[Ni_{1-x}^{2+} Fe_{1+x}^{3+}]O_4^{2-}$ [2]. Zn^{2+} is diamagnetic and its main effect is to break linkages between magnetic cations. Another effect is to increase interaction distance by expanding the unit cell, since it has an ionic radius larger than the Ni and Fe radii. The most remarkable effect is that substitution of this diamagnetic cation (Zn) results in a significant increase in magnetic moment in a number of spinel solid solutions, Fig. 2.11.

Figure 2.11. Variation of Magnetic moment (in Bohr magnetons per formula unit) with increasing zinc substitution [1, 2].

Magnetic moment as a function of Zn content shows an increase for small substitutions, goes through a maximum for intermediate values, decreases and finally vanishes for high Zn contents

A simple analysis shows that this increase can be expected for an antiparallel alignment. As the Zn content increases, magnetic moments decrease in sublattice A and increase in sublattice B . If the magnetic moment of Fe and Ni are 5 and $\sim 2.3 \mu_B/\text{ion}$, respectively, then, per formula unit, the total moment in Bohr magnetons on B sublattice is $2.3(1-x) + 5(1+x)$ and on A sublattice the total antiparallel moment is $5(1-x)$. If the resultant moment per formula unit is $M_s(0)$, then by taking the difference of A and B moments [15],

$$\begin{aligned} M_s(0) &= 2.3(1-x) + 5(1+x) - 5(1-x) \\ &= x(10 - 2.3) + 2.3 \end{aligned}$$

A linear relationship is obtained with a slope of 7.7 , predicting a moment value of $10 \mu_B$ per formula unit for Zn substitution $x=1$, as shown by the broken lines in Fig. 2.11. This relationship is not followed over the entire composition range. However, as the Zn content increases, $A-O-B$ interactions become too weak and $B-O-B$ interactions begin to

dominate. That is, the average distance between the interacting spins gets larger. As a consequence, the system becomes frustrated causing a perturbation to the magnetically ordered spins as large number of B sites spins gets non-magnetic impurity atoms as their nearest neighbors.

Figure 2.12. Schematic representation of spin arrangements in $Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$: (a) ferrimagnetic (for $x \leq 0.5$); (b) triangular or Yafet-Kittel (for $x > 0.5$); and (c) antiferromagnetic for $x \approx 1$.

The B spins are no longer held in place due to this weak anti-ferromagnetic A - B interaction leading to non-collinearity or canting among the B sublattice. Thus for $x > 0.5$ Zn content, instead of a collinear antiparallel alignment, canted structure appears, where spins in B sites are no longer parallel [2, 21], Fig. 2.12. Evidence of this triangular structure has been observed by neutron diffraction [20]; a theoretical analysis showed that departure from collinear order depends on the ratio of the $A-O-B$ to $B-O-B$ molecular field coefficients, $\lambda_{AB} / \lambda_{BB}$ [23]. For high Zn concentration, $B-O-B$ interactions dominant and the ferrite become antiferromagnetic for $x = 1$ [2].

2.7 Microstructure

A polycrystal is much more than many tiny crystals bonded together. The interfaces between the crystals, or the *grain boundaries* which separate and bond the grains, are complex and interactive interfaces. The whole set of a given material's properties (mechanical, chemical and especially electrical and magnetic) depend strongly on the nature of the microstructure.

In the simplest case, the grain boundary is the region, which accommodates the difference in crystallographic orientation between the neighbouring grains. For certain simple arrangements, the grain boundary is made of an array of dislocations whose number and spacing depends on the angular deviation between the grains. The ionic nature of ferrites leads to dislocation patterns considerably more complex than in metals, since electrostatic energy accounts for a significant fraction of the total boundary energy [2].

For low-loss ferrite, Ghate [1] states that the grain boundaries influence properties by

- 1) creating a high resistivity intergranular layer,
- 2) acting as a sink for impurities which may act as a sintering aid and grain growth modifiers,
- 3) providing a path for oxygen diffusion, which may modify the oxidation state of cations near the boundaries.

In addition to grain boundaries, ceramic imperfections can impede domain wall motion and thus reduce the magnetic property. Among these are pores, cracks, inclusions, second phases, as well as residual strains. Imperfections also act as energy wells that pin the domain walls and require higher activation energy to detach. Stresses are

microstructural imperfections that can result from impurities or processing problems such as too rapid a cool. They affect the domain dynamics and are responsible for a much greater share of the degradation of properties than would expect [1].

Grain growth kinetics depends strongly on the impurity content. A minor dopant can drastically change the nature and concentration of defects in the matrix, affecting grain boundary motion, pore mobility and pore removal [2, 23]. The effect of a given dopant depends on its valence and solubility with respect to host material. If it is not soluble at the sintering temperature, the dopant becomes a second phase which usually segregates to the grain boundary.

Figure 2.13. Porosity character: (a) intergranular, (b) intragranular.

The porosity of ceramic samples results from two sources, intragranular porosity and intergranular porosity, Fig. 2.13. An undesirable effect in ceramic samples is the formation of exaggerated or discontinuous grain growth which is characterized by the excessive growth of some grains at the expense of small, neighbouring ones, Fig. 2.14. When this occurs, the large grain has a high defect concentration. Discontinuous growth is believed to result from one or several of the following: powder mixtures with impurities; a very large distribution of initial particle size; sintering at excessively high temperatures; in ferrites containing *Zn* and /or *Mn*, a low O_2 partial pressure in the sintering atmosphere. When a very large grain is surrounded by smaller ones, it is called ‘duplex’ microstructure.

Figure 2.14. Grain growth (a) discontinuous, (b) duplex (schematic).

2.8 Theories of Permeability

Permeability is defined as the proportionality constant between the magnetic field induction B and applied field intensity H [2, 19, 25]:

$$B = \mu H \quad (2.7)$$

If the applied field is very low, approaching zero, the ratio will be called the initial permeability, Fig. 2.15 and is given by

$$\mu_i = \frac{\Delta B}{\Delta H}_{(\Delta H \rightarrow 0)}$$

This simple definition needs further sophistications. A magnetic material subjected to an ac magnetic field can be written as

$$H = H_0 e^{i\omega t} \quad (2.8)$$

It is observed that the magnetic flux density B lag behind H . This is caused due to the presence of various losses and is thus expressed as

$$B = B_0 e^{i(\omega t - \delta)} \quad (2.9)$$

Here δ is the phase angle that marks the delay of B with respect to H . The permeability is then given by

$$\mu = \frac{B}{H} = \frac{B_0 e^{i(\omega t - \delta)}}{H_0 e^{i\omega t}} = \frac{B_0 e^{-i\delta}}{H_0} = \frac{B_0}{H_0} \cos \delta - i \frac{B_0}{H_0} \sin \delta = \mu' - i\mu'' \quad (2.10)$$

where
$$\mu' = \frac{B_0}{H_0} \cos \delta \quad (2.11)$$

and
$$\mu'' = \frac{B_0}{H_0} \sin \delta \quad (2.12)$$

The real part (μ') of complex permeability (μ), as expressed in equation (2.10) represents the component of B which is in phase with H , so it corresponds to the normal permeability. If there are no losses, we should have $\mu = \mu'$. The imaginary part μ'' corresponds to that of B , which is delayed by phase angle 90° from H [15, 19]. The presence of such a component requires a supply of energy to maintain the alternating magnetization, regardless of the origin of delay. The ratio of μ'' to μ' , as is evident from equation (2.12) and (2.11) gives

$$\frac{\mu''}{\mu'} = \frac{\frac{B_0}{H_0} \sin \delta}{\frac{B_0}{H_0} \cos \delta} = \tan \delta \quad (2.13)$$

This $\tan \delta$ is called loss factor.

The quality factor is defined as the reciprocal of this loss factor, i.e.

$$\text{Quality factor} = \frac{1}{\tan \delta} \quad (2.14)$$

And the relative quality factor, $Q = \frac{\mu'}{\tan \delta}$ (2.15)

Figure 2.15. Schematic magnetization curve showing the important parameter: initial permeability, μ_i (the slope of the curve at low fields) and the main magnetization mechanism in each magnetization range.

The curves that show the variation of both μ' and μ'' with frequency are called the magnetic spectrum or permeability spectrum of the material [15]. The variation of permeability with frequency is referred to as dispersion. The measurement of complex permeability gives us valuable information about the nature of domain wall and their movements. In dynamic measurements the eddy current loss is very important. This occurs due to the irreversible domain wall movements. The permeability of a ferrimagnetic substance is the combined effect of the wall permeability and rotational permeability mechanisms.

2.8.1 Mechanisms of Permeability

The mechanisms can be explained as follows: A demagnetized magnetic material is divided into number of Weiss domains separated by Bloch walls. In each domain all the magnetic moments are oriented in parallel and the magnetization has its saturation value M_s . In the walls the magnetization direction changes gradually from the direction of magnetization in one domain to that in the next. The equilibrium

positions of the walls result from the interactions with the magnetization in neighboring domains and from the influence of pores; crystal boundaries and chemical inhomogeneities which tend to favour certain wall positions.

2.8.1.1 Wall Permeability

The mechanism of wall permeability arises from the displacement of the domain walls in small fields. Lets us consider a piece of material in the demagnetized state, divided into Weiss domains with equal thickness L by means of 180° Bloch walls (as in the Fig. 2.16). The walls are parallel to the YZ plane. The magnetization M_s in the domains is oriented alternately in the $+Z$ or $-Z$ direction. When a field H with a component in the $+Z$ direction is applied, the magnetization in this direction will be favoured. A displacement dx of the walls in the direction shown by the dotted lines will decrease the energy density by an amount [26, 27]:

$$\frac{2M_s H_z dx}{L}$$

This can be described as a pressure $M_s H_z$ exerted on each wall. The pressure will be counteracted by restoring forces which for small deviations may assume to be kdx per unit wall surface. The new equilibrium position is then given by

$$d = \frac{M_s H_z dx}{L}$$

From the change in the magnetization

$$\Delta M = \frac{2M_s d}{L},$$

the wall susceptibility χ_w may be calculated. Let H makes the angle θ with Z direction. The magnetization in the θ direction becomes

$$(\Delta M)_\theta = \frac{2M_s d}{L} \cos\theta, \text{ And with } H_z = H \cos\theta \text{ and } d = \frac{2M_s H_z}{K}$$

we obtain

$$\chi_w = \frac{(\Delta M)_\theta}{H} = \frac{4M_s^2 \cos^2 \theta}{KI}. \quad (2.16)$$

Figure 2.16. Magnetization by wall motion and spin rotation.

2.8.1.2 Rotational Permeability

The rotational permeability mechanism arises from rotation of the magnetization in each domain. The direction of M can be found by minimizing the magnetic energy E as a function of the orientation. Major contribution to E comes from the crystal anisotropy energy. Other contributions may be due to the stress and shape anisotropy. The stress may influence the magnetic energy via the magnetostriction. The shape anisotropy is caused by the boundaries of the sample as well as by pores, nonmagnetic inclusions and inhomogeneities. For small angular deviations, α_x and α_y may be written as

$$\alpha_x = \frac{M_x}{M_s} \text{ and } \alpha_y = \frac{M_y}{M_s}.$$

For equilibrium Z -direction, E may be expressed as [24, 25]

$$E = E_0 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_x^2 E_{xx} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_y^2 E_{yy}$$

where it is assumed that x and y are the principal axes of the energy minimum. Instead of E_{xx} & E_{yy} , the anisotropy field H_x^A and H_y^A are often introduced. Their magnitude is given by

$$H_x^A = \frac{E_{xx}}{2M_s} \text{ and } H_y^A = \frac{E_{yy}}{2M_s},$$

H_x^A & H_y^A represent the stiffness with which the magnetization is bound to the equilibrium direction for deviations in the x and y direction, respectively. The rotational susceptibilities $\chi_{r,x}$ and $\chi_{r,y}$ for fields applied along x and y directions, respectively are

$$\chi_{r,x} = \frac{M_s}{H_x^A} \text{ and } \chi_{r,y} = \frac{M_s}{H_y^A}.$$

For cubic materials it is often found that H_x^A and H_y^A are equal. For $H_x^A = H_y^A = H^A$ and a field H which makes an angle θ with the Z direction (as shown in Fig. 2.16) the rotational susceptibility, $\chi_{r,c}$ in one crystallite becomes

$$\chi_{r,c} = \frac{M_s}{H^A} \sin^2 \theta \quad (2.17)$$

A polycrystalline material consisting of a large number of randomly oriented grains of different shapes, with each grain divided into domains in a certain way. The rotational susceptibility χ_r of the material has to be obtained as a weighted average of $\chi_{r,c}$ of each crystallite, where the mutual influence of neighbouring crystallites has to be taken into account. If the crystal anisotropy dominates other anisotropies, then H^A will be constant throughout the material, so only the factor $\sin^2 \theta$ (equation 2.17) has to be averaged. Snoek [26] assuming a linear averaging of $\chi_{r,c}$ and found

$$\chi_r = \frac{2M_s}{3H^A}$$

The total internal susceptibility

$$\chi = \chi_w + \chi_r = \frac{4M_s^2 \cos^2 \theta}{KL} + \frac{2M_s}{3H^A} \quad (2.18)$$

If the shape and stress anisotropies cannot be neglected, H^A will be larger. Any estimate of χ_r will then be rather uncertain as long as the domain structure, and the pore distribution in the material are not known. A similar estimate of χ_w would require knowledge of the stiffness parameter k and the domain width L . These parameters are influenced by such factors as imperfection, porosity and crystallite shape and distribution which are essentially unknown.

References

- [1] Goldman, A., Handbook of Modern Ferromagnetic Materials, Kulwer Acad. Pub, Boston, U.S.A 1999.
- [2] Valenzuela, R., Magnetic Ceramics, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 1994.
- [3] M. M. Haque, "Influence of additives on the magnetic and electrical properties of iron-excess Mn-Zn ferrites," M. Phil. Thesis, BUET, Bangladesh 2000.
- [4] J. Tasaki and T. Ito., *Intl. Conf. On Ferrite*, Japan, 1970.
- [5] T. Nakamura., "Low-temperature sintering of Ni-Zn-Cu ferrite and its permeability spectra," *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, Vol-168, pp 285, 1997.
- [6] E. Roess, *Ferrites*, U. of Tokyo Press, Tokyo, Vol-187, 1971).
- [7] Hoque, S.M., Ullah, M. S., Khan, F.A., Hakim, M.A., Shaha, D.K., "Structural and magnetic properties of Li-Cu mixed spinel ferrites", *Physica B*, Vol-406, pp 1799-1804, 2011
- [8] Vivek verma., Gailora, S.P., Mohan, C., Mathpal,S., Annapoorni, R.K., Kotnala., "Magnetic and electrical properties of manganese and cadmium co-substituted lithium ferrites". *J.Alloys compd.* Vol-481, pp 872-876, 2009.

-
- [9] N. Rezlescu, E. Rezlescu, C. Pasnicu and M. L. Craus, "Effects of the rare-earth ions on some properties of a nickel-Zinc ferrite," *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter*, vol- 6, pp 5707, 1994.
- [10] E. Rezlescu, L. Sachelarie, P. D. Popa and N. Rezlescu, "Effect of substitution of divalent ions on the electrical and magnetic properties of Ni-Zn-Me ferrites," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, Vol-36, pp 3962, 2000.
- [11] A. Globus, 2nd *EFS*.
- [12] M. I. Rosales, E. Amano, M. P. Cuautle and R. Valenzuela, "Impedance spectroscopy studies of Ni-Zn ferrites," *Materials Science and Engineering*, Vol-B49, pp 221, 1997.
- [13] M. El-Shabasy, "DC electrical properties of Ni-Zn ferrites," *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, Vol- 172, pp 188, 1997.
- [14] B. D. Cullity, *Introduction to Magnetic Materials*, Addison-Wisley Publishing Company, Inc., California, 1972.
- [15] M. A. Wahab, *Solid State Physics: Structure and Properties of Materials*, Narosa Publishing House, New Delhi , 1999.
- [16] F. Brailsford, *Physical Principles of Magnetism*, D. Van Nostrand Company Ltd., London , 1966.
- [17] A. J. Dekker, *Solid State Physics*, Macmillan India Ltd., New Delhi ,1998.
- [18] S. Chikazumi, *Physics of Magnetism*, Jhon Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1966.
- [19] C. Kittel, *Introduction to Solid State Physics*, 7th edition, Jhon Wiley & Sons, Inc., Singapore, 1996.
- [20] A. K. M. Akther Hossain, M. Seki, T. Kawai and H. Tabata, "Colossal magnetoresistance in spinel type $Zn_{1-x}Ni_xFe_2O_4$," *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol-96, pp 1273 , 2004.
- [21] N. S. Satya Murthy, M. G. Natera and S. I. Youssef, "Yafet-Kittel angles in nickel-zinc ferrites," *Physical Review*, Vol-181, pp 969, 1969.
- [22] Y. Yafet and C. Kittel, "Antiferromagnetic arrangements in ferrites," *Physical Review*, Vol-87, pp 290, 1952.
- [23] M. F. Yan and D. W. Johnson, "Impurity induced exaggerated grain growth in Mn-Zn ferrites," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol- 61, pp 342, 1978.
- [24] D. Hadfield., *Permanent Magnets and Magnetism*, Jhon Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York 1962.
- [25] S. S. Sikder, "Temperature dependence of magnetization and induced magnetic anisotropy of some Fe, Co and Ni-based amorphous ribbons," *Ph. D. Thesis*, BUET, Bangladesh ,1999.

- [26] K. M. A. Hussain, "Study of complex permeability and secondary effects in some cobalt and manganese based ferrites," *M. Phil. Thesis*, BUET, Bangladesh, 2003.
- [27] J. L. Snoek, "Dispersion and absorptions in magnetic ferrites at frequencies above Mc/s," *Physica*, Vol-14, pp 207, 1948.

CHAPTER 3

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

In this chapter we describe basic experimental techniques to measure the lattice parameters, particle size and frequency dependent AC permeability of ferrite samples.

3.1 Composition of the studied ferrite system

In the present research Li-Cu-Mn based soft ferrites are synthesized and thoroughly investigated. The ferrites under investigation are:

3.2 Sample preparation

A goal common to all the ferrites is the formation of the spinel structure. Now a day, the majority of ferrite powders are made by the conventional Ceramic process or Solid State Reaction technique. Most of the non-conventional processes are involved in producing the powder by a wet method. Among these methods, some are [1, 2]:

- 1) Co-precipitation
- 2) Organic precursors
- 3) Sol-gel synthesis
- 4) Spray-drying
- 5) Freeze-drying
- 6) Combustion synthesis
- 7) Glass crystallization

In this chapter, we describe the combustion method that is used in this research work.

3.3 Combustion method

Combustion method a novel method for preparation of fine particles of ferrites makes use of the strong exothermic reaction between metal nitrate and fuel. In this processes, the stoichiometric ratio of nitrates is dissolve in the minimum amount of ethanol in a glass beaker and starrier it until all the nitrate salts completely soluble in the ethanol. The mixed solution was then evaporated on a constant temperature water bath. After boiling and ignition of the mixture, a spinel residue is obtained in a few minutes. A heating rate of at least $75^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ is used to obtained good combustion. These powders are crushed and ground thoroughly. Low temperature calcinations have to perform. The calcined powders are again crushed into fine powders. The pellet and toroid-shaped samples are prepared from these calcined powders using die-punch assembly or hydrostatic or isostatic pressure. Sintering is carried out, at temperature ranging $1200\text{-}1350^{\circ}\text{C}$, for times of typically 1-40 h and in various atmospheres (e.g. Air, O_2 and N_2) [3-6]. Fig. 3.1 shows diagrammatically, the stages followed in ferrite preparation.

Figure 3.1. Flow chart of the stages in preparation of spinel ferrite

There are basically four steps in the preparation of ferrite:

- 1) Preparation of materials to form an intimate mixture with the metal nitrate in the ratio which they will have in the final product,
- 2) Heating of this mixture to form the ferrite (often called calcining),
- 3) Grinding the calcined powders and pressing the fine powders into the required shape, and
- 4) Sintering to produce a highly dandified product.

The calcining process can be repeated several times to obtain a high degree of homogeneity. The calcined powders are crushed into fine powders. The ideal characteristics of fine powders are [2]:

- 1) small particle size (sub micron)
- 2) narrow distribution in particle size
- 3) dispersed particles
- 4) equiaxed shape of particles
- 5) high purity
- 6) homogeneous composition.

A small particle size of the reactant powders provides a high contact surface area for initiation of the solid state reaction; diffusion paths are shorted, leading to more efficient completion of the reaction. Porosity is easily eliminated if the initial pores are very small. A narrow size distribution of spherical particles as well as a dispersed state is important for compaction of the powder during green-body formation. Grain growth during sintering can be better controlled if the initial size is small and uniform.

A binder is usually added prior to compaction, at a concentration lower than 5wt % [2]. Binders are polymers or waxes; the most commonly used binder in ferrite is polyvinyl alcohol. The binder facilitates the particles flow during compacting and increases the bonding between the particles, presumably by forming bonds of the type particle-binder-particle. During sintering, binders decompose and are eliminated from the ferrite. Pressures are used for compacting very widely but are commonly several tons per square inch (i. e., up to 10^8 N m^{-2}).

Sintering is defined as the process of obtaining a dense, tough body by heating a compacted powder for a certain time at a temperature high enough to significantly promote diffusion, but clearly lower than the melting point of the main component. The

driving force for sintering is the reduction in surface free energy of the powder. Part of this energy is transferred into interfacial energy (grain boundaries) in the resulting polycrystalline body [2, 7]. The sintering time, temperature and the furnace atmosphere play very important role on the magnetic property of ferrite materials. The purposes of sintering process are:

- 1) to bind the particles together so as to impart sufficient strength to the product,
- 2) to densify the material by eliminating the pores and
- 3) to homogenize the materials by completing the reactions left unfinished in the calcining step.

Sintering of crystalline solids is dealt by Coble and Burke [8] who found the following empirical relationship regarding rate of grain growth:

$$\bar{d} = kt^n \quad (3.1)$$

where \bar{d} is the mean grain diameter, n is about $1/3$, t is sintering time and k is a temperature dependent parameter. Sintering is divided into three stages, Fig. 3.2 [2, 9].

Stage 1. Contact area between particles increases,

Stage 2. Porosity changes from open to closed porosity,

Stage 3. Pore volume decreases; grains grow.

Figure 3.2. Schematic representation of sintering stages: (a) greenbody, (b) initial stage, (c) intermediate stage, and (d) final stage.

In the initial stage, neighbouring particles form a neck by surface diffusion and presumably also at high temperatures by an evaporation-condensation mechanism. Grain growth begins during the intermediate stage of sintering. Since grain boundaries are the sinks for vacancies, grain growth tends to decrease the pore elimination rate due to the increase in distance between pores and grain boundaries, and by decreasing the total grain boundary surface area. In the final stage, the grain growth is considerably enhanced and the remaining pores may become isolated.

In *Ni-Zn* ferrites, the presence of *Zn* complicates the sintering process because high temperature coupled with low oxygen firing will cause *Zn* loss. High density is important for high permeability, but so is *Zn* conservation. Tasaki [1] described two alternative firings to achieve high density:

- 1) Low sintering temperature excluding O_2 (Vacuum, argon, nitrogen),
- 2) High temperature in pure oxygen to reduce *Zn* loss.

Accordingly, other properties correlated along with density:

- 1) Lattice constant is greater for O_2 , smaller for vacuum
- 2) Curie temperature is greater for vacuum, smaller for O_2
- 3) Resistivity is greater for O_2 , smaller for vacuum.

3.4 Preparation of the present samples

Nanocrystalline $Li_xCu_{0.12}Mn_{0.88-2x}Fe_{2+x}O_4$ ($x = 0, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.4$ and 0.44) ferrites were prepared by combustion technique. The analytical grade of $Li(NO_3)_2$, $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ and $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ are weighted according to the stoichiometric amount and dissolved in ethanol. The mixture was placed in a constant temperature bath at $70^\circ C$, followed by an ignition, the combustion takes place within a

few seconds and fine nanosized powders were precipitated. These powders were crushed and ground thoroughly. The fine powders of various compositions are then calcined at 900°C for 5 h for the final formation of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ferrites nano-particles. Then the fine powders are granulated using Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) as a binder and pressed into disk- and toroid-shaped samples. The samples are sintered at various temperatures (1150, 1200, 1250, 1300 and 1350°C) in air for 1 hour. The temperature ramps for sintering are 5°C/min for heating, and 10°C/min for cooling.

3.5 X-ray diffraction

Bragg reflection is a coherent elastic scattering in which the energy of the X-ray is not changed on reflection. If a beam of monochromatic radiation of wavelength λ is incident on a periodic crystal plane at an angle θ and is diffracted at the same angle as shown in Fig. 4.1, the Bragg diffraction condition for x-rays is given by

$$2d \sin \theta = n\lambda \quad (3.2)$$

where d is the distance between crystal planes and n is the positive integer which represents the order of reflection. Equation (4.1) is known as Bragg law. This Bragg law suggests that the diffraction is only possible when $\lambda \leq 2d$ [10]. For this reason we cannot use the visible light to determine the crystal structure of a material. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) provides substantial information on the crystal structure.

Figure 3.3: Bragg law of diffraction.

X-ray diffraction was carried out with an X-ray diffractometer for the samples $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ (with $x = 0.00, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40$ and 0.44). For this purpose monochromatic Cu-K_α radiation was used. The lattice parameter for each peak of each sample was calculated by using the formula

$$a_0 = d\sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}, \quad (3.3)$$

where h , k and l are the indices of the crystal planes. To determine the exact lattice parameter for each sample, Nelson-Riley method was used. The Nelson-Riley function $F(\theta)$ is given as

$$F(\theta) = \frac{1}{2} \left[(\cos^2 \theta / \sin \theta) + (\cos^2 \theta / \theta) \right] \quad (3.4)$$

The values of lattice constant 'a' of all the peaks for a sample are plotted against $F(\theta)$. Then using a least square fit method exact lattice parameter 'a₀' is determined. The point where the least square fit straight line cut the y-axis (i.e. at $F(\theta) = 0$) is the actual lattice parameter of the sample.

The physical or bulk densities ρ_B of the samples were determined by Archimedes principle with water medium using the following expression [11]:

$$\rho_B = \frac{W\rho}{W - W'} \text{ g / cm}^3 \quad (3.5)$$

where W is the weight of the sample in air, W' is the weight of the sample in the water and ρ is the density of water in room temperature.

The theoretical density ρ_{th} was calculated using following expression:

$$\rho_{th} = \frac{8M}{N_A a_o^3} \text{ g / cm}^3 \quad (3.6)$$

Where N_A is Avogadro's number ($6.02 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), M is the molecular weight. The porosity was calculated from the relation $\{100(\rho_{th} - \rho_B)/\rho_{th}\}\%$, where ρ_B is the bulk density measured by Archimedes principle.

3.6 Study of microstructure

The micro structural study was performed in order to have an insight of the grain structures. The samples of different compositions and sintered at different temperatures were chosen for this purpose. The samples were visualized under a high-resolution optical microscope and then photographed. Average grain sizes (grain diameter) of the samples were determined from optical micrographs by linear intercept technique [3]. To do this, several random horizontal and vertical lines were drawn on the micrographs. Therefore, we counted the number of grains intersected and measured the length of the grains along the line traversed. Finally the average grain size was calculated.

3.7 Average particle size measurement

Particle size determination is important in the ferrite nanoparticles. Due to their small particle size significant fine particle broadening is observed in the Bragg peaks. A crystal is usually considered perfect when atoms occupy all lattice sites and no imperfection exists in the crystal. The broadening of diffraction peaks arises mainly due to three factors. The peaks become broader due to the effect of small crystallite sizes and thus an analysis of peaks broadening can be use to determine the crystallite sizes introduce additional broadening into the diffraction peaks.

The condition for constructive interference, reinforcement of X-ray scattering from a crystalline powder is given by Bragg's law which is given by Eq: 3.6:

$$2d \sin \theta = n\lambda \quad (3.6)$$

This equates the path difference of X-ray scattered from parallel crystalline planes spaced $d = d_{hkl}$ apart to an integral (n) number of X-ray wavelength λ . Here θ is the diffraction angle measured with respect to the crystalline planes. For an infinite crystal Bragg scattering occurs at discrete values of 2θ satisfying the Bragg condition, i.e. Bragg peaks are δ -function. For finite sized crystals the peaks are broadened over a range of angle.

To understand the phenomenon of fine particle broadening following argument of Cullity [4], we consider a finite crystal of thickness, $D = md$, where m is an integer and d is the distance between crystal planes, i.e. there are m planes in D.

Figure 3.4. Effect of fine particle size on diffraction curves (Schematic): (a). small particle size and (b) large particle size

Considering Fig 3.4, if the broadened Bragg peak begins at an angle $2\theta_2$ and ends at $2\theta_1$, the breadth of the peaks or full width at half maximum (FWHM) is given as:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2}(2\theta_1 - 2\theta_2) = (\theta_1 - \theta_2) \quad (3.7)$$

Now if we consider the path differences for each of the two angles θ_1 and θ_2 for X-ray traveling the full thickness of the crystal. The width β is usually measured in radians. We now write path difference equations for these two angles, related to the entire thickness of the crystal rather to the distance between adjacent planes

$$2D \sin \theta_1 = (m+1)\lambda \quad (3.8)$$

$$2D \sin \theta_2 = (m-1)\lambda \quad (3.9)$$

By subtraction we find:

$$D(\sin \theta_1 - \sin \theta_2) = \lambda \quad (3.10)$$

$$D2 \cos\left(\frac{\theta_1 + \theta_2}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\theta_1 - \theta_2}{2}\right) = \lambda \quad (3.11)$$

But θ_1 and θ_2 are both very nearly equal to θ , so that $\theta_1 + \theta_2 \approx 2\theta$ and

$\sin\left(\frac{\theta_1 - \theta_2}{2}\right) \approx \left(\frac{\theta_1 - \theta_2}{2}\right)$. So that equation (3.11) can be written as:

$$D2 \cos\left(\frac{2\theta}{2}\right) \left(\frac{\theta_1 - \theta_2}{2}\right) = \lambda$$

$$\text{or, } D2 \cos \theta \left(\frac{\theta_1 - \theta_2}{2} \right) = \lambda \quad (3.12)$$

From equation (3.7) and equation (3.12) we get

$$D\beta \cos \theta = \lambda \quad (3.14)$$

$$\text{Or, } D = \frac{\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (3.15)$$

A more exact empirical treatment yields

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (3.16)$$

This is known as the Scherer's formula. It is used to estimate the particle size of very small crystal from the measured width of their diffraction curves.

3.8 Complex initial permeability measurement

For high frequency application, the desirable property of a ferrite is high permeability with low loss. One of the most important goals of ferrite research is to fulfill this requirement. The techniques of permeability measurement and frequency characteristics of the present samples are described in sections 3.8.1 and 3.8.2

3.8.1 Techniques for the initial permeability measurement

Measurements of permeability normally involve the measurements of the change in self-inductance of a coil in presence of the magnetic core. The behavior of a self-inductance can now be described as follows. We assume an ideal loss less air

coil of inductance L_0 . On insertion of a magnetic core with permeability μ , the inductance will be μL_0 . The complex impedance Z of this coil [1] can be expressed as follows:

$$Z = R + jX = j\omega L_0 \mu = j\omega L_0 (\mu' - j\mu'') \quad (3.17)$$

where the resistive part is $R = \omega L_0 \mu''$ (3.18)

and the reactive part is $X = \omega L_0 \mu'$ (3.19)

The RF permeability can be derived from the complex impedance of a coil, Z , given by equation (3.17). The core is taken as toroidal to avoid demagnetizing effects. The quantity L_0 is derived geometrically as shown in section 3.8.2.

3.8.2 Frequency characteristics of the present samples

The frequency characteristics of the ferrite samples i.e. the initial permeability spectra were investigated using a Wayne Kerr Electronics impedance (model no. 4192A) and Wayne Kerr Precision Impedance Analyzer (model no. 6500B). The complex permeability measurements on toroid shaped specimens were carried out at room temperature on all the samples in the frequency range 10 kHz – 120 MHz. The real part (μ'_i) and imaginary part (μ''_i) of the complex permeability were calculated using the following relations [4]: $\mu'_i = L_s / L_0$ and $\mu''_i = \mu'_i \tan \delta$, where L_s is the self-inductance of the sample core and $L_0 = \mu_o N^2 S / \pi \bar{d}$ is derived geometrically. Here L_0 is the inductance of the winding coil without the sample core, N is the number of turns of the coil ($N = 5$), S is the area of cross section of the toroidal sample as given below:

$$S = d \times h,$$

where
$$d = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{2},$$

d_1 = Inner diameter,

d_2 = Outer diameter,

h = Height

and \bar{d} is the mean diameter of the toroidal sample as given below:

$$\bar{d} = \frac{d_1 + d_2}{2}$$

The relative quality factor is determined from the ratio $\frac{\mu'_i}{\tan \delta}$.

References

- [1] Goldman, A., Handbook of Modern Ferromagnetic Materials, Kulwer Acad. Pub, Boston, U.S.A 1999.
- [2] Valenzuela, R., Magnetic Ceramics, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 1994.
- [3] Akther Hossain, A. K. M., "Investigation of colossal magnetoresistance in bulk and thick film magnetites," Ph. D. Thesis, Imperial College, London 1998.
- [4] Cullity, B. D.; Introduction to Magnetic Materials, Addison-Wisley Publishing Company, Inc., California 1972.
- [5] Brook, R. J., *Sintering: An Overview, Concise Encyclopedia of Advanced Ceramic Materials*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, pp. 438, 1991.
- [6] Reijnen, P., Science of Ceramics, Academic Press, London, 1967.
- [7] W. D. Kingery, W. D., Bowen, H. K., and Uhlman, D. R, Introduction to Ceramics, 2nd edition, Wiley Interscience, New York, pp 476, 1976.
- [8] Coble, R. L. and Burke, J. E.; 4th Int. Symp. On the Reactivity of Solids, Amsterdam, pp. 38-51 1960.

- [9] McColm, I. J., and Clark, N. J., "Forming, Shaping and Working of high Performance Ceramics", Blackie, Glasgow, pp 1-338 , 1988.
- [10] Kittel, C., Introduction to Solid State Physics, 7th edition, Jhon Wiley & Sons, Inc., Singapore 1996.
- [11] Gadkari, A. B., Shinde, T. J., Vasambekar, P. N., "Structural and magnetic properties of nanocrystalline Mg-Cd ferrites prepared by oxalate co-precipitation method," J. Mater Sci: Mater Electron, Vol. 21(1), pp 96-103, 2010.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The nanocrystalline $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ($x=0.00, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40, 0.44$), are studied. All ferrites are sintered at various temperatures (1150, 1200, 1250, 1300 and 1350 °C) for one hour in air. Structural and surface morphology are studied by X-ray diffraction and optical microscopy. The magnetic properties of the ferrites are characterized with high frequency (100Hz-120MHz) complex permeability. The effects of Li substitution and sintering temperature on the complex permeability of these ferrites are discussed.

4. Investigation of polycrystalline $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$

4.1. Structural analysis

4.1.1. X-ray Diffraction analysis

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed to verify the formation of spinel structure of various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ferrites, in which Mn^{2+} is replaced by Li^+ and Fe^{3+} . The XRD patterns of these Li^{+1} substituted $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ (with $x = 0.00, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40$ and 0.44) ferrites sintered at 1200°C in air for 1h are shown in Fig. 4.1. The results indicated that these materials have a well defined single crystalline phase and formation of cubic spinel structure for each composition. Analyzing the XRD patterns it is observed that the positions of the peaks comply with the reported value [1] and some traces of raw materials (Fe_2O_3 and MnO) were found for $x=0.00$, $x=0.10$ & $x=0.20$ and $x=0.30$).

Fig. 4.1. The X-ray diffraction patterns for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$.

4.1.2 Lattice constant

The values of lattice constant obtained from each plane are plotted against Nelson-Riley function [2]. The values of lattice constant were estimated from the extrapolation of these lines to $F(\theta) = 0$ or $\theta = 90^\circ$. Fig. 4.2 shows that the lattice constant, a_0 as a function of lithium content for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1200°C . It is noticed from Fig.5.2 that the lattice constant increases with increasing of Li^+ content in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ (with $x = 0.00, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40, 0.44$) ferrites. Values of lattice constant for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ are presented in the Table 4.1.

Fig. 4.2. Variation of lattice constant with Li content for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1200°C

The increase in lattice constant with Li content indicates that the present system obeys the Vegard's law [3]. This increase of lattice constant can be attributed to the ionic size differences since the unit cell has to expand when substituted by ions with large

ionic size. The ionic radius of Li^+ (0.76Å) is greater than that of Mn^{2+} (0.67Å) [4-5]. When the larger Li^+ and Fe^{3+} ions enter the lattice, the unit cell expands while preserving the overall cubic symmetry.

4.1. 3. Average particle size

The average particle size was estimated by using Debye-Scherrer [6] formula from the broadening of the highest intensity peaks (311) of XRD patterns

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta},$$

where D is the average particle size, λ is the wavelength of the radiation used as the primary beam of $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda=1.54178 \text{ \AA}$), θ , is the angle of the incident beam in degree and β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the fundamental reflection (311) in radian of the FCC ferrites phase. Debye-Scherer's formula assumes approximation and gives the average particle size if the grain size distribution is narrow and strain induced effects are quite negligible.

Fig.4.3. XRD patterns of (311) peak with Li content, x for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles.

Fig. 4.3 shows the XRD patterns of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ferrites sintered at 1200°C for 1 h, where (311) peak is shown in expanded form to understand the variation of FWHM of the Bragg peaks with the Li content. From this figure it is seen that the value of FWHM decreases with increasing lithium content. The particle size of the sample is inversely proportional to FWHM according to Debye-Scherrer formula. The observed particle size is in the range 9.4 nm to 30 nm which are listed in the Table 4.2

4.1.4 Density and Porosity

The bulk density ρ_B of each composition of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ferrites sintered at different temperatures is measured by Archimedes's principle. The theoretical density, ρ_{th} and the porosity, P of each sample were calculated using Eq-4.4 and Eq-4.5, respectively. The values of ρ_{th} and ρ_B for the various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ (with $x = 0.00, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40, 0.44$) are tabulated in the Table-4.1.

Fig. 4.4. The variation of X-ray density and bulk density with Li for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$

It is noticed from Fig. 5.4 that both ρ_{th} and ρ_B decrease with increasing Li substitution in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ for constant sintering temperature. This phenomenon could be explained in terms of the atomic weight. The atomic weight of Mn (54.94 amu) is greater than combined atomic weight of the Li (6.941 amu) and Fe (55.845 amu) [4]. On the other hand, the P increases with increasing Li content in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ (with $x = 0.00, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, 0.40, 0.44$) ferrites. It is also observed that the ρ_B of each sample increases with increasing sintering temperatures, whereas the P follows the opposite trend. It is known that the porosity of the ceramic samples results from two sources, intragranular porosity and intergranular porosity. When the grain growth rate is very high, pores may be left behind by rapidly moving grain boundaries, resulting in pores that are trapped inside the grains. This intragranular porosity leads to poor magnetic and mechanical properties. Thus, the total porosity could be written as $P = P_{intra} + P_{inter}$. The intergranular porosity mainly depends on the grain size [7]. At higher sintering temperatures grain formed uniformly and voids reduced as a result density increases.

4.2. Microstructures

The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ (where $x = 0.00, x = 0.10, x = 0.20, x = 0.30, x = 0.40$ and $x = 0.44$) are shown in Figs. 4.5, 4.6 and 4.7 sintered at 1200, 1250 and 1300°C, respectively. Average grain sizes (D) of all samples are determined from optical micrographs by linear intercept technique [5]. The D is significantly dependent on Li substitution. The D increases with increasing Li substitution for fixed sintering temperature. It is also observed that D increases with increasing sintering

temperatures which is shown in the Fig. 5.8. The values of D for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: The lattice parameter, sintering temperature, T_s , density, porosity, and average grain size of the $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ samples sintered at various temperatures with fixed dwell time 1h.

(x)	a_o (Å)	T_s (°C)	ρ_{th} (g/cm ³)	ρ_B (g/cm ³)	Porosity (%)	Average Grain Size(μm)	μ_i' (at 70 kHz)
0.00	8.3370	1150	5.32	4.77	10	15.12	
		1200		4.82	10	17.92	18
		1250		4.84	9	20.45	19
		1300		4.89	8	20.85	28
		1350		4.561	14	56.67	22
0.10	8.3615	1150	5.15	4.61	11	38.69	
		1200		4.62	10	19	22
		1250		4.64	10	26.25	22
		1300		4.69	9	30	38
		1350		4.499	13	79.68	42
0.20	8.3746	1150	5.02	4.54	10	28.57	
		1200		4.58	9	39	33
		1250		4.62	8	26.48	40
		1300		4.65	8	32	40
		1350		4.456	11	133.33	44
0.30	8.3866	1150	4.90	4.42	10	25.83	
		1200		4.44	9	92	39
		1250		4.48	9	28.67	43
		1300		4.50	8	77.67	58
		1350		4.375	11	166.66	45
0.40	8.4024	1150	4.76	4.37	8	35	
		1200		4.41	8	145.45	50
		1250		4.44	7	257.14	51
		1300		4.47	6	220.58	65
		1350		4.203	12	318.75	45
0.44	8.4091	1150	4.66	4.29	8	37.5	
		1200		4.3	8	295.45	55
		1250		4.34	7	300	62
		1300		4.38	6	321.42	90
		1350		4.139	11	485.71	130

Fig. 4.5. The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1200°C

Fig.4.6. The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1250°C

Fig.4.7. The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1300°C

Fig. 4.8. The optical micrographs of $\text{Li}_{0.4}\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.08}\text{Fe}_{2.40}\text{O}_4$ sintered at different temperatures.

Table 4.2: Particle size and FWHM of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ samples

x	FWHM (in degree)	Particle size (nm)
0.00	0.015379	9.4
0.10	0.00733	19
0.20	0.006109	23
0.30	0.004712	30
0.40	0.004887	30
0.44	0.005411	27

4.3 Complex permeability

The compositional variation of complex permeability spectra for the $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ samples sintered at 1200, 1250 and 1300°C are shown in Fig. 5.9. The real part of initial permeability (μ'_i) increases with increasing Li^+ content for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ for a fixed sintering temperature. On the other hand the resonance frequency is found to decrease with Li substitution. It is observed that the μ'_i of $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ferrite increases from 28 to 90 sintered at 1300°C. It is also observed that the μ'_i remains constant for the samples up to the resonance frequency, f_r . A sharp decrease in μ'_i and increase in μ''_i is observed above the f_r .

Fig.4.9: The μ_i' and μ_i'' for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at (a) 1200, (b) 1250 and (c) 1300°C in air.

Fig.4.10: The μ_i' and grain size for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ sintered at 1200°C in air.

Fig. 4.11: The μ_i' with lithium content for various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$. Sintered at 1200°C , 1250°C and 1300°C in air.

The μ'_i values increase with the increase of sintering temperatures. The values of μ'_i for all samples are presented in the Table 4.1.

The permeability of polycrystalline ferrite is related to two different magnetizing mechanisms: spin rotation and domain wall motion [8, 9], which can be described as, $\mu'_i = 1 + \chi_w + \chi_{spin}$, where χ_w is the domain wall susceptibility, χ_{spin} is intrinsic rotational susceptibility. χ_w and χ_{spin} may be written as: $\chi_w = 3\pi M_s^2 D / 4\gamma$ and $\chi_{spin} = 2\pi M_s^2 / K_u$ with M_s saturation magnetization, K_u the total anisotropy, D the grain diameter, and γ the domain wall energy. The Fig. 4.10 shows that the μ'_i and D as a function of Li content sintered at 1200°C. It is also observed from the Fig. 5.11 that μ'_i increases with increasing sintering temperature.

According the Globus and Duplex model [10] the μ'_i can be explained as $\mu'_i = \frac{M_s^2 D}{\sqrt{K}}$, where M_s is the saturation magnetization and K is the magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant. This increase in permeability is expected, because grain size of all samples increase with Li content. It is known that the mobility of domain walls is greatly affected by the microstructure of ferrites. Therefore in the present case, variation of the initial permeability may be influenced by its grain size.

The large grains favor domain wall mobility, giving rise to high permeability. Therefore, the high values of initial permeability in the present samples can also be attributed to the high grain sizes of the samples.

Moreover, the magnetic properties of soft ferrite are strongly influenced by its composition, additives and microstructures of the material. Among all these factors, the microstructures have great influence on magnetic properties. It is generally believed that

larger the grain sizes, the higher the saturation magnetization and initial permeability. In microstructure studies of the present ferrite system, it is also observed that D increases with the function of Li content.

The increasing value of μ_i' with the increase of sintering temperature is due to the lower porosity for samples sintered at higher sintering temperature. As sintering temperature increases pores and voids are reduced with increasing sintering temperature. Similar trend was observed by Guillaud in Mn-Zn ferrite [11].

The variation of loss factor, $\tan\delta (= \mu_i'' / \mu_i')$ with frequency for all samples has been studied. Fig.4.12 shows the variations of loss factors with frequency for $Li_xCu_{0.12}Mn_{0.88-2x}Fe_{2+x}O_4$ ferrites sintered at 1200, 1250 and 1300°C, respectively.

At lower frequencies magnetic loss is observed and remains constant up to a certain frequency, 9 MHz; this frequency limit depends upon the sintering temperatures. The lag of domain wall motion with respect to the applied magnetic field is responsible for magnetic loss and this is accredited to lattice imperfections [12]. At higher frequencies, a rapid increase in loss factor is observed. A resonance loss peak is shown in this rapid increase of magnetic loss. At the resonance, maximum energy transfer occurs from the applied field to the lattice which results in the rapid increase in loss factor.

As it is observed that phase lag between domain rotations and applied field is greater than that between applied field and domain wall displacement, the magnetic losses due to domain rotation override those due to domain wall displacement [13-14].

Fig. 4.12. Loss factor as a function of frequency with Li content sintered at (a) 1200, (b) 1250 and (c)

1300°C

Fig. 4.13: The variation of relative quality factor with frequency for $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$.

samples sintered at (a) 1200 °C and (b) 1250 °C (c) 1300 °C

The loss factor is also observed to increase with the increase of sintering temperature. The variation of initial loss with frequency for the various $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ferrite in the sintering temperature range 1200°C – 1300°C is shown in Fig. 4.12. The increase in sintering temperature results in increased Li loss in the samples, thereby creating defects in the lattice, which gives rise to magnetic loss.

From the loss factor, the Q -factor is calculated. The relative quality factor (Q -factor) versus frequency plots of all the samples sintered at 1200, 1250 and 1300°C are shown in Fig. 5.13. It can be seen that the value of Q -factor increases with an increase of frequency and shows a peak around 3 MHz. The Q increases with increasing sintering temperature. Among all the studied samples, highest value of Q -factor (=2165) is observed for $x=0.40$ sintered at 1300°C .

References

- [1] Rath, C., Anand, S., Das, R., P., Sahu, K., K., Kulkarni, S., D., Date, S., K., Mishra, N., C., dependence of cation distribution of particle size, lattice parameter and magnetic properties in nanosize Mn-Zn ferrites”, J. Appl. Phys. Vol-91(4), pp 2211, 2002.
- [2] Nelson, J., B., Riley, D., P., ‘An experimental investigation of extrapolation methods in the derivation of accurate unit-cell dimensions of crystals”, Proc. Phys. Soc. London, Vol-57, pp 160, 1945.
- [3] Vegard, L., “The constitution of mixed crystal and the space occupied by atom”, Phys. Vol-5, pp 17, 1921.
- [4] Winter, M. J., www.webelements.com,©, University of Sheffield, UK, 1995-2006.
- [5] Mendelson, M., I., Ceram, J., Am.; Soc. 52(8), pp 443, 1967.
- [6] Cullity, B. D., Elements of X-ray diffraction, Reading” 3rd edition-Wesley, 1972.
- [7] Chauhan, B. S., R. Kumar, K. M. Jadhav and M. Singh “Magnetic study of substituted Mn ferrites synthesized by citrate precursor method” J. Magn. Mater. Vol-283, pp 71-81, 2004.

-
-
- [8] Kang, S. H., and Yoo, H.I., “The effect of nonstoichiometry (δ) on the magnetic properties of $(\text{Mg}_{0.22}\text{Mn}_{0.07}\text{Fe}_{0.71})_{3-\delta}\text{O}_4$ ferrite”, *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol-88, pp 4754-4757, 2000.
- [9] Caltun, O. F. and Spinu, L., “Magnetic properties of high frequency NiZn ferrites doped with CuO”, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, Vol-37(4), pp 2353-2355, 2001.
- [10] Globus, A., Duplex, p., and Gytot, “Determination of initial magnetization curve crystallize size and effect anisotropy field” *IEE, Trans. Magn.* Vol-7, pp 617-622, 1971.
- [11] Guillaud, C., “The properties of manganese-zinc ferrites and the physical processes governing them”, *Proc. IEEE*, Vol-104B, pp 165-173, 1957.
- [12] Snoek, J. L., “Dispersion and absorption in magnetic ferrites at frequencies above one Mc/s”, *Physica*, Vol-17(4), pp 207, 1948.
- [13] Hu Jun and Yan Mi, “Preparation of high permeability Ni-Cu-Zn ferrites”, *J. Zhej. Univ. Sci.*, Vol-6B (6), pp 580, 2005
- [14] Tsutaoka, T, Ueshima, T, Tokunaga, T., Nakamura, T, and Hatakeyama, K., “Frequency dispersion and temperature variation of complex permeability of Ni-Zn ferrite composite materials” *J. Appl. Phys.* Vol-78(6), pp 3983, 1995.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ ($x=0.00-0.44$) nanoparticles have been successfully synthesized by the combustion technique. Nanoparticles size has been determined from the broadening of the highest intensity peaks (311) of XRD patterns by using Debye-Scherrer formula. The observed particle size is in the range from 9 to 30 nm. The XRD patterns confirm that the samples are single phase and form cubic spinel structure. The lattice parameter increases linearly with increasing Li content and obeys the Vegard's law. This is due to greater ionic radius of Li ion than that of Mn ion. The study of microstructure shows that grain size increases with increasing *Li* content in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$ samples. This is probably due to the lower melting temperature of *Li* (180°C) compared to Mn (1245°C).

The bulk density decreases with increasing *Li* substitution in $\text{Li}_x\text{Cu}_{0.12}\text{Mn}_{0.88-2x}\text{Fe}_{2+x}\text{O}_4$. This phenomenon could be explained in terms of the atomic weight. The atomic weight of *Li* (6.941 amu) is smaller than that of the *Mn* (54.94 amu). It is also observed that the experimental density of all samples increases and porosity decreases with increasing sintering temperatures. The increase in density and decrease in porosity with sintering temperatures are expected because during sintering process, the thermal energy generates a force that drives the grain boundaries to grow over pores, thereby decreasing the pore volume and hence the material becomes denser.

The real part of initial permeability μ_i' increases with increasing *Li* content for a fixed sintering temperature. This result can be explained with the help of average grain

size. The μ_i' increases with increasing of sintering temperatures for all samples because of the microstructure are homogeneous with large grain size and a uniform size distribution. The highest μ_i' is found 90 for $x=0.44$ which is three times greater than that of parent composition. The real part of initial permeability remains fairly constant in the frequency range up to some critical frequency which is called resonance frequency, f_r . As the Li content increases in $Li_xCu_{0.12}Mn_{0.88-2x}Fe_{2+x}O_4$ samples, the resonance frequency, f_r for $Li_xCu_{0.12}Mn_{0.88-2x}Fe_{2+x}O_4$ samples decreases. It is observed that the resonance frequency, f_r and real part of initial permeability, μ_i' are inversely proportional which really confirm Snoek's relation, $f_r \mu_i' = \text{constant}$.

The relative quality factor increases with increasing sintering temperature. The maximum Q value (2165) is found for $x=0.4$ sintered at 1300°C .

5.2 Suggestions for future work

Magnetization and Neél temperature can be measured for characterization of its magnetic properties. It was found that among the $Li_xCu_{0.12}Mn_{0.88-2x}Fe_{2+x}O_4$ ferrites $Li_{0.44}Cu_{0.12}Fe_{2.44}O_4$ had the maximum initial permeability μ_i' and maximum Q -factor is found for $Li_{0.4}Cu_{0.12}Mn_{0.08}Fe_{2.4}O_4$. So divalent and trivalent cations can be substituted in $Li_xCu_{0.12}Mn_{0.88-2x}Fe_{2+x}O_4$ ferrite to enhance its magnetic properties. Sintering additives like Bi_2O_3 and V_2O_5 can be mixed to promote densification and getting better result in lower sintering temperatures to magnetic materials.